

Factors contributing to Burnout and Turnover Intentions in International School and University Guidance Counsellors.

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ABSTRACT:

Burnout and high turnover rates in counselling communities are areas of growing concern, yet no research to date has examined these issues in school counselling professionals based overseas. As such, this study examined factors influencing burnout and turnover intentions in international school and university guidance counsellors.

Job Satisfaction Scale (JSS), Counselor Burnout Inventory (CBI), Quantitative Workload Inventory (QWI), and Turnover Intention Scale (TIS) were utilised. Responses to an online survey were collected from 158 individuals registered with the International School Counselor Association (ISCA) and the International Association for College Admissions Counseling (IACAC). Correlational and hierarchical regression analyses were performed to investigate these factors. Participants reported overall ambivalence toward their jobs, and moderate to high levels of burnout. The significance of geographical region was also addressed.

Findings demonstrated that age and interference of non-counselling duties significantly predicted burnout. Hierarchical regression analysis revealed that these factors were moderated by job satisfaction variables (salary, fringe benefits, co-workers, nature of work, communication, and workload).

Interference of non-counselling duties emerged as a significant predictor of turnover intentions but was offset in influence upon the introduction of additional variables. The final results revealed that geographical region, operating conditions, lack of time for curriculum implementation, and effectiveness of intra-organisational communication were most significant in predicting turnover intentions in international school counsellors.

Understanding the factors associated with burnout and turnover intentions within this community may help shed light on how to address these issues in international schools. Further investigation is necessary to distinguish influencing factors within specific regions.

Keywords: international education, school counselling, counsellor burnout, job satisfaction, turnover intentions

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1. INTRODUCTION AND RATIONALE

It is now a widely accepted fact, that educating the community about mental health and socio-emotional wellbeing provides a plethora of benefits with regard to social emotional development and student growth (Watts and Kidd, 2000), including positive academic outcomes (Henry, 1996; Davies, 1991; Thomas and Smith, 2004), improved school engagement (Barnard, 2003), decreasing problem behaviours (Hill and Taylor, 2004) and reported greater levels happiness and life satisfaction (Jia et al., 2009; Peterson et al., 2007). There is also consensus that key stakeholders involved in delivering personal social and emotional curricula and educating the school community are professional school or guidance counsellors (Inman et.al., 2009; Walker, 2010). The American Psychological Association Dictionary of Psychology (Vandenbos, 2007), defines school counselling as follows:

“guidance—offered at school or elsewhere to students, parents, and other caregivers—that focuses on students’ academic, personal, social, and career adjustment, development, and achievement.”

For simplicity, the term ‘school counsellor’ will be used in this essay to encompass these duties and responsibilities. Nevertheless, role definition and role ambiguity will be discussed throughout.

Originally coined by Freudenberger (1974), the definition of burnout has been applied to the occupational context to define an emerging syndrome as a result of chronic workplace stress. Three main characteristics of burnout include exhaustion, increased dissatisfaction and pessimism, and reduced work efficiency (Moyer, 2011; WHO, 2019).

Research into burnout over the last few decades has recognised its seriousness and the significant impact it has on professionals working in therapeutic settings in particular, including mental health and support workers, psychologists, psychiatrists, school guidance counsellors, and social workers (Lambie, 2007; Moyer, 2011; Skovholt, 2001; Wilkerson and Bellini, 2006).

A British Psychological Society report in 2016 “found that 70% of psychotherapists found their job stressful, with a quarter considering themselves to have a long-term chronic condition, 46% reported depression” (McCormack et.al., 2018). Moreover, some literature argues that burnout is prevalent in counselling roles, affecting 39% of all mental health professionals (Lambie, 2007; Moyer, 2011), with the average working life span of a counsellor equating to 10 years (Grosch and Olsen, 1994). Additional research estimates that on average 10-20 percent of school counsellor educators experience dissatisfaction with their job, which in turn could make them susceptible to burnout (Wilkerson and Bellini, 2006). Moreover, burnout has been reportedly identified as a considerable risk factor associated with turnover intention (Alarcon, 2011; Kim and Kao, 2014), which is, in turn, arguably a direct precursor to leaving the profession (Mobley, 1977; Parasuraman, 1982; Jeswani and Dave, 2012).

While these numbers are reported from studies conducted on school counselling and counselling populations, the studies in question largely focused on addressing their specific and immediate contexts, with the majority conducted in the United States (e.g. Maslach et.al., 1996; Baggerly and Osborn, 2006; Moyer, 2011; Bardhoshi et.al., 2014). There is no study to date that looks at factors contributing to burnout, or factors influencing turnover intentions among international school counsellor educators. It would be particularly valuable to explore how these influences translate into an international setting, as average annual turnover ranges at international schools have reportedly increased from 20 to 30 percent (Reeves and Wigford, 2008; Odland and Ruzicka, 2009; Mancuso et.al., 2010; Roberts et.al., 2010; Tkachyk, 2017).

Working overseas (China and Malaysia) in international schools between 2012-2017, I have witnessed first-hand the rapid turnover in the international community, heard the anecdotally reported high levels of stress and burnout among school counselling colleagues, and personally experienced effects of burnout and issues leading to job dissatisfaction. In addition to numerous contributing factors, the general consensus among colleagues was the need for a universal outline of the role responsibilities and a unified definition of terms when referring to school or guidance counselling. Nevertheless, as these were personal and anecdotal, I wanted to explore the topic to confirm whether there was more to these informal exchanges.

The purpose of this study was therefore to determine the factors that are significant in contributing to burnout and turnover intentions, as well as exploring whether there are particular factors within different regions that could explain and predict burnout and turnover intentions in international communities.

1.2. LITERATURE REVIEW

1.2.1 Brief History of School Counselling: Then and Now

Burnout and turnover intentions have been linked to a lack of role definition, set responsibilities, and overall ambiguity surrounding the term school counselling and guidance (Coll and Freeman, 1997; Lambie, 2007; Scarborough and Culbreth, 2008; Wilkerson and Bellini, 2006; Wilkerson, 2009). In order to understand and contextualise the significance of these factors, we must explore the history and changing definition of the role of the school counsellor.

The term “guidance” as a system of providing support to pupils in educational settings has existed since before the 20th century (Best et.al., 1995; Morris, 1955; Watts and Kidd, 2000). Nevertheless, the modern elements of school counselling that encompass pastoral care and social-emotional development only began to be implemented in the late 1960s (Best et.al., 1995; Dogan, 1999; Tatar, 2000; Gysbers and Henderson, 2001). This was largely due to legislative changes in education in the UK and US (Best, et.al., 1995; Elias et. al., 1997; Buck et.al., 1998; Collins and McNiff, 1999; Watts and Kidd, 2000), which meant that schools experienced a shift in how personal social and emotional education was perceived: moving from a reactive to a proactive approach, emphasising educating the whole child inclusive of personal and social wellbeing (Best et al., 1995; Lee-Man and Luk-Fong, 2013; Watts and Kidd, 2000; Wylie, 2005).

Greater attention was now given to developing and implementing personal and social education programmes, with an attempt to embed those within the school curriculum (Gysbers, 2004; Hui, 2000; Watts and Kidd, 2000). During this transitory period, there emerged a need to update the role and responsibilities that came with it.

Previously, guidance oftentimes meant a mentoring relationship. However, educational institutions were increasingly finding themselves in need of specialist staff trained in a variety of counselling approaches (Leung, 2003; Inman et.al., 2009) in order to deliver a comprehensive curriculum and offer pupils access to counselling interventions (Gysbers, 2004; Lee-Man and Luk-Fong, 2013) to help them make changes, learn, and grow (Lee-Man and Luk-Fong, 2013).

Research in the 1990s was already shedding light on this shift (Crawford et.al., 1998; Edwards et.al., 1998; Lee and Ekstrom, 1987), with guidance and counselling staff expressing concerns that the time spent on counselling activities was unbalanced due to other demands, and highlighting that the result was that some students were overlooked (Edwards et.al., 1998).

While it is undeniable that progress has been made over the past few decades in the development and implementation of systems of support in educational institutions worldwide (Aira et. al, 2014; Bemak, 2000; Lee-Man and Luk-Fong, 2013; Keyes, 2005; Watts and Kidd, 2000) many schools still struggle to provide a clear definition of the role and responsibilities of professionals involved in developing these programmes and promoting personal, social and emotional wellbeing in students (Bemak, 2000; Brown et.al., 2011; Paisley and McMahon, 2001).

1.2.2. The Global Lens

Acceleration in globalisation in the past decades, led to increased economic and personal mobility, which in turn led to changes in the educational context; a number of developing countries not only saw a rise in international establishments but also in international schools catering to expatriate communities (Lauder, 2007). In recent years, many international schools are opening their doors to local populations, as increasing numbers of students wish to pursue Western-style education (Creemers et. al, 2002; Lauder, 2007; Song et.al, 2016; Yen, 2008).

This shift in international educational priorities also resulted in an increased need for professional school counselling staff. Moreover, in order to cater to diverse

communities, it is necessary for these individuals to be trained in multiple counselling approaches (Inman et.al., 2009; Giordano, 1997; Jing and Zuo, 2000; Leung, 2003), and to be cognisant of nuances of university application processes for international students, as part of the draw of local communities to international schools is the ability to pursue higher education abroad (Creemers et. al, 2002).

The result of the aforementioned lack of clear responsibilities for the role is that school counsellors employed internationally find themselves in an extremely diverse environment, faced with rising job demands and a broad remit (Carey et.al., 2017; Gysbers et.al., 1999; Inman et.al., 2009). These demands include provision of counselling services to groups or individuals to cater to a variety of social and emotional needs; PSHE-type programme creation and management; psycho-educational school-community outreach; educational testing; career and university advising; parental engagement; oversight of child protection and safeguarding policies; and consulting with teachers (Bardhoshi et.al., 2014; Butler and Constantine, 2005; Fitch et.al., 2001; Kuranz, 2002; Scarborough and Culbreth, 2008). This list is not exhaustive, and school counsellors are required to perform duties not related to expectations of the role, for example administrative tasks such as lunch duty (Bardhoshi et.al., 2014; Butler and Constantine, 2005; Scarborough and Culbreth, 2008), or are expected to perform tasks with conflicting job responsibilities, such as disciplining students (Bemak, 2000; Coll and Freeman, 1997).

In the implementation of personal, social emotional and career guidance curriculums, deviations from the standards and norms that do exist (such as those provided by SEED, 2004; Euroguidance, 2018; ASCA, 2005; PSHE Association, 2019) are seen across schools, districts, counties, and countries. It is reasonable to anticipate that these inconsistencies, uneven distribution of responsibilities, and additional duties (Brown et.al., 2011; Carey et.al., 2017; Cunningham and Sandhu, 2000; Inman et.al., 2009; Paisley and McMahon, 2001), may translate to burnout and job dissatisfaction, leading to high turnover numbers in these communities (Butler and Constantine, 2005; Scarborough and Culbreth, 2008).

1.3. BURNOUT AND CONTRIBUTING FACTORS

Burnout is described as a long-term chronic “physical and emotional exhaustion resulting from conditions at work” (Blase, 1982; Freudenberg, 1974; Maslach and Jackson, 1986; Osborn, 2004). Upon the term’s coinage and introduction in 1974, research into the construct began. Maslach and Jackson developed the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI; Maslach and Jackson, 1986), which further defined three distinct dimensions which represent burnout: emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation, and reduced personal accomplishment (Maslach and Jackson, 1986; Maslach, 2001). Symptoms may include physical (e.g., exhaustion), cognitive (e.g., increased dissatisfaction and pessimism), emotional (e.g., feeling helpless), and behavioural properties (e.g., reduced work efficiency) (Lambie, 2007; Moyer, 2011; WHO, 2019). Early research into occupational burnout mainly targeted health-care providers (Bakker et al., 2014; McCormack et.al., 2018). However, with the evolution of counsellor roles within the education setting, studies began to explore burnout in those communities (Bardhoshi et. al., 2014; Coll and Freeman, 1997). Lee et. al. (2007, 2010) developed a Counselor Burnout Inventory (CBI) that drew on Maslach’s research and added extra dimensions, which focused on therapeutic relationships in particular (exhaustion, incompetence, negative work environment, devaluing client, and deterioration in personal life).

Lambie (2007) argued that burnout affects 39% of mental health professionals, while Kesler (1990) argued that counsellors are particularly vulnerable to burnout due to high levels of stress resulting from role ambiguity, increasing job demands and unique factors pertinent to the counselling relationship, such as compassion fatigue (Figley, 2002; Kesler, 1990; Skovholt, 2001).

Burnout can result from individual, environmental and situational, organisational, and developmental factors, and can manifest in stages over time (Lawson, 2007; Maslach et.al., 2001). Various physical and environmental factors have been examined as possible contributors (Bardhoshi et. al., 2014; Lee et. al., 2007; Pugliesi, 1999; Spector, 1997).

Studies that specifically targeted job satisfaction as contributing stressors in school counsellors found that lack of clarity in defining their roles and responsibilities were primary causes of stress and burnout when levels of job satisfaction among those

populations were reported as low (Bryant and Constantine, 2006; Coll and Freeman, 1997). Previous research has also identified additional unique factors that contribute to stress and burnout in school counselling communities: student caseload and lack of supervision (Baggerly and Osborn, 2006; Wilkerson and Bellini, 2006; Wilkerson, 2009). These are outlined below.

1.3.1. Role Ambiguity

Lack of clarity of role definition and interference of additional duties with core counselling responsibilities have been reported to play a significant role in perceived burnout in school counselling communities (Kirk-Brown and Wallace, 2004; Lee et.al., 2007). Some standards of role definition and expectations do exist. For example, in the United States, these are determined by the American School Counselor Association (ASCA, 2005), while in European countries these can be found on the Euroguidance website (Euroguidance, 2018).

ASCA (2005) defines the role of the school counsellor and outlines their responsibilities: “guidance—offered at school or elsewhere to students, parents, and other caregivers—that focuses on students’ academic, personal, social, and career adjustment, development, and achievement”. While not concrete, the definition helps to shed light on the intended focus of the job. Nevertheless, Lieberman (2004) argued that despite existing standards, school counsellors are frequently expected to carry out extra tasks outside of this remit.

Bardhoshi et.al. (2014) outlined the most common additional duties and responsibilities frequently assigned to school counsellors: lunch and bus duty, engaging in extra-curricular activities, scheduling, external testing coordination and supervision, special education services, class supervision, discipline (Bardhoshi et.al., 2014; Gysbers and Henderson, 2001). Additional expectations to complete administrative and clerical tasks have been an ongoing concern among the school counselling community, as it makes it increasingly difficult for them to see students, leading to counsellors feeling overwhelmed (Bryant and Constantine, 2006; Kolodinsky et.al., 2009). Chata and Loesch (2007) argued that stressors of role ambiguity, role conflict, and confusion may additionally stem from administrators’ lack of understanding as to what the role entails

and the amount of time required for counselling duties (Lieberman, 2004; Cervoni and DeLucia-Waack, 2011).

The inconsistency within the profession with regards to set responsibilities has been reported to lead to role confusion (Lieberman, 2004), with role ambiguity in particular having been linked to high levels of exhaustion examined by burnout inventories (CBI; Lee et al., 2007; MBI; Maslach and Jackson, 1986).

Based on previous research, role ambiguity and the interference of extra duties not relating to core counselling responsibilities was identified as a large contributing factor, and was therefore addressed in the current study by collecting information through specific questions.

1.3.2. Supervision

Benefits of supervision for school counsellors has been extensively researched, highlighting improving effectiveness of service delivery, personal growth, accountability, confidence, and professional development (Baggerly and Osborn, 2006; Bernard and Goodyear, 2009; McMahon and Patton, 2001; Wood and Rayle, 2006). Baggerly and Osborn (2006) argued that clinical supervision is imperative for school counsellors precisely due to role ambiguity.

It has been argued that while school counsellors do provide early, brief, interventions, their role within a school is not equivalent to a role in a clinical setting, therefore removing the need for supervision all together (Lawson, 2007). Nevertheless, supervision has been consistently reported as a factor in burnout in school counsellors (Baggerly and Osborn, 2006; Moyer, 2011), where engaging in supervision has been linked to decreased levels of burnout, and positively correlated with career satisfaction (Baggerly and Osborn, 2006).

Despite this, professional clinical supervision is not mandated by professional associations (Dollarhide and Saginak, 2012). Additionally, Borders and Usher (1992) found that once qualified, school counsellors receive less supervision compared to other professionals working in the mental health settings. When this is the standard set by

national bodies that exist to provide guidance for operational procedures and policies for schools to draw upon, the outlook for educational institutions operating internationally is particularly grim.

Due to the significance of supervision in previous research, this factor was included as a potential contributor to burnout and examined in the current study through a subscale of the Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS; Spector, 1997).

1.3.3. Caseload

Caseload, or student to counsellor ratio, was reportedly linked to the effectiveness of school counsellors in their role (Baker and Gerler, 2008).

There is no literature to date that specifically looks at caseload of students per school counsellor in international schools. Existing regional research indicates that ASCA (2005) recommends the ratio not to exceed 250 students per one school counsellor, and that higher student to counsellor ratios decrease effectiveness and increase burnout (Bardhoshi et.al., 2014; McCarthy et.al., 2010; Wilkerson, 2009). Moyer (2011), however, reported that caseload was not a significant factor in predicting burnout in school counsellors.

Professional accreditation bodies (eg. WASC¹, CIS²) that acknowledge the need for a school counsellor to be present in the school, do not specify the number of school counsellors needed for each grade level, nor determine the limits of students per counsellor. As caseload is a potential factor of overwork and burnout, despite conflicting findings in previous research (Maslach, 2001), it was examined as a contributing variable in the current study.

1.3.4. Job Satisfaction

¹ Western Association of Schools and Colleges (WASC)

² Council of International Schools (CIS)

A plethora of research exists into the significance of the relationship between job satisfaction and burnout (DeMato and Curcio, 2004; Rupert et.al., 2015). Early research into job satisfaction in school counsellors revealed particularly low levels of job satisfaction (Baggerly and Osborn, 2006). Moreover, previous research showed that there is a significant link between job satisfaction and burnout in therapeutic and counselling professions (Alarcon, 2011; Bryant and Constantine, 2006; Lee et.al., 2011). DeMato and Curcio (2004) identified that the main factor associated with increased levels of job dissatisfaction in school counsellors was engagement in duties not related to the counselling role, while Clemens et.al. (2009) argued that more engagement with core counselling responsibilities may lead to higher levels of job satisfaction (Baggerly and Osborn, 2006; Clemens et.al., 2009). This is consistent with findings later presented by Moyer (2011).

Existing literature suggests that job satisfaction is interconnected with aforementioned components unique to the school counselling profession, such as role ambiguity, work overload, and supervision. Previous research, however, focused on the relationship between job satisfaction as a whole and burnout in school counsellors (Bardhoshi et.al., 2014; Mullen et.al., 2020; Mullen et.al., 2021), with very few considering separate occupation-related components that may contribute to burnout. Leinbaugh et.al.'s (2003) study was one of the first to separate areas that could contribute to job satisfaction when considering counselling populations. They introduced sub-groupings of organisational control, internal control and time and effort management. Even so, the study examined job satisfaction in relation to turnover intentions in counselling educators as faculty members (Leinbaugh et.al., 2003; Sangganjanavanich and Balkin, 2013).

In addition, job demands, excessive workload, working conditions, and job characteristics such as having autonomy over one's tasks have been associated with burnout and turnover intentions (Demerouti et al., 2001; Grant et.al., 2019; Russell, 2017). Due to the complex picture painted by role ambiguity and nuances of schools operating in an international setting, it is pertinent to examine job satisfaction in an attempt to understand burnout within the international community. The current study therefore sought to shed light on the relationship between job satisfaction and burnout,

and examine whether particular components related to job satisfaction acted as significant predictors in determining burnout in the international sample.

1.3.5. Additional Contributing Factors

Previous research revealed additional physical and environmental factors associated with burnout and turnover intentions in school counselling communities, such as age (Iacovides et.al., 2003; Maslach, 2001), gender (Maslach, 2001; Purvanova and Muros, 2010), race and ethnicity (Bryant and Constantine, 2006; Maslach, 2001), years of experience (Butler and Constantine, 2005; Wilkerson, 2009), specific role (Coll and Freeman, 1997; Baggerly and Osborn, 2006), and setting (Wachter et.al., 2008). The current study drew on previous research to examine whether there is a link between job satisfaction, caseload, role ambiguity, and turnover intentions in the sample consisting of school and university guidance counsellors operating internationally. Demographic data was collected and taken into account to examine whether these factors play a significant role in predicting burnout and turnover intentions; information was collected on participant's age, gender, years of experience, type of school, specific role and operational setting.

1.4. TURNOVER INTENTIONS

Turnover and employee retention are topics of concern for most organisations, bearing obvious costly consequences of having to attract and train new talent (Knudsen et.al., 2006). Turnover in counselling professions adds additional elements of impact on programme management and delivery of care, as well as disruption to on-going client relationships (Barak et.al., 2001; Lum et.al., 1998). Burnout and job satisfaction have been discussed as significant factors in relation to turnover intentions (Clemens et.al., 2009; Knudsen et.al., 2006; Mullen et.al., 2020), and turnover intention was in turn established as a precursor to actual turnover (Griffeth et.al., 2000; Jeswani and Dave, 2012; Parasuraman, 1982).

Clemens et.al. (2009) highlighted concern over a shortage of school counsellors, which continues to be the case with high rates of turnover in counselling professions (Gallon et.al., 2003; Knudsen et.al., 2006), with work-related stress, role ambiguity, and

job dissatisfaction cited as being at forefront of the matter (Barling et.al., 2005; Clemens et.al., 2009).

Turnover and turnover intentions have largely eluded research literature as a topic of investigation in international settings, and existing literature on turnover in international schools is limited (Reeves and Wigford, 2008; Odland and Ruzicka, 2009; Mancuso et.al., 2010). There is a major gap in literature in examining the impact of job satisfaction and burnout on turnover intentions in international school counsellors and how that impacts students.

Existing data on turnover rates of all educators in international schools, showed that the average length of employment of teachers was equal to 2.3 years; for administrators (i.e. Head of School, Principal) the average number of years of staying in one location was 3.7 years (Mancuso et.al., 2010; Benson, 2011).

Turnover in international school communities has been consistently high for decades, with early studies reporting annual turnover rates at 23% as a norm (Odland and Ruzicka, 2009). Later studies, however, report mixed findings: annual turnover rate for EARCOS³ collaborative schools was at 32% (Roberts et.al., 2010); Bunnell (2014) suggests that operational the norm of annual turnover rates in international schools is 30%. However, Desroches (2013) examined turnover figures in international schools operating within large international governing bodies (AASSA, ECIS, NES⁴), and found that turnover rates ranged from 0 to 83% (Desroches, 2013; Mancuso et.al., 2010). These figures may be on the rise, as a result of the growing international school market and the shortage of professionals willing to relocate internationally (Brummitt, 2007; Brummitt and Keeling, 2013; Hayden, 2011; Mancuso et.al., 2010; Odland and Ruzicka, 2009).

Due to the high costs associated with replacing a teacher or administrator in international schools (Gilbert, 2011; Martinez et.al., 2010) and a well-acknowledged fact that frequent turnover of teachers negatively impacts student's academic achievement and the school community as a whole (Darling-Hammond and Sykes,

³ East Asia Regional Council of Schools (EARCOS)

⁴ Association of American Schools in South America (AASSA), Educational Collaborative for International Schols (ECIS), New South Wales Education Standards Authority (NESA)

2003; Ronfeldt et al. 2011; Russell, 2017; Varlas, 2013), it is not surprising that attention has been diverted to employee retention and understanding turnover in international school in the last decade in the hope to avert “the quiet crisis in international school recruitment” (Reeves and Wigford, 2008).

Some work has been done to determine factors influencing turnover in expatriate educators; salary, working conditions, and leadership remain dominant factors in job dissatisfaction and influence turnover intentions in the international market (Mancuso et.al., 2010; Oddland and Ruzicka, 2009).

There is no study to date that explores the significance that demographic, psychological, and environmental factors have on burnout and turnover intentions in school counsellors in international communities. With such stark variance in turnover figures, it is necessary to examine what these factors look like within this setting. Moreover, as turnover intention is considered to be a precursor to actual turnover (Parasuraman, 1982), understanding associated factors may help international schools reduce turnover of their school counselling populations. This study therefore aims to fill this gap in research by recognizing that there may be nuances particular to international contexts. This study aims to reveal a clearer picture of experiences in these communities, which in turn should pave the way for future investigation and the development of strategies to support the school counselling populations in question.

1.5. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

To address the aforementioned factors, three research questions were examined:

Research Question One: Are the following demographic, environmental, and psychological variables significant predictors of the level of burnout in international school counsellors: age, gender, region, years of experience, type of school (private or public), role and responsibilities, caseload, pay, chances of professional growth and promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, operating conditions, relationship with co-workers, job tasks themselves, intra-organisational communication, workload, curriculum implementation, interference of non-counselling duties?

Null Hypothesis 1: Demographic, environmental, and psychological variables **are not** significant predictors of burnout in international school counsellors.

Alternative Hypothesis 1: Demographic, environmental, and psychological variables **are** significant predictors of burnout in international school counsellors.

Research Question Two: Can the following demographic, environmental, and psychological factors be used to explain turnover intention in international school counsellors: age, gender, region, years of experience, type of school (private or public), role and responsibilities, caseload, pay, chances of professional growth and promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, operating conditions, relationship with co-workers, job tasks themselves, intra-organisational communication, workload, curriculum implementation, interference of non-counselling duties, exhaustion, incompetence, devaluing client, negative work environment, deterioration to personal life?

Null Hypothesis 2. Demographic, environmental, and psychological factors **cannot** be used to explain turnover intention in international school counsellors.

Alternative Hypothesis 2. Demographic, environmental, and psychological factors **can** be used to explain turnover intention in international school counsellors.

Research Question Three: Does region play a significant role in burnout and turnover intentions of international school counsellors?

Null Hypothesis 3(a): Region is **not** a significant factor in predicting burnout in international school counsellors.

Alternative Hypothesis 3(a): Region **is** a significant factor in predicting burnout in international school counsellors.

Null Hypothesis 3(b): Region is **not** a significant factor in predicting turnover intentions in international school counsellors.

Alternative Hypothesis 3(b): Region **is** a significant factor in predicting turnover intentions in international school counsellors.

CHAPTER 2: METHODOLOGY

2.1. STUDY DESIGN

One of the strongest merits of quantitative methodology is the ability to collect large scale data in a limited amount of time (Cohen et al., 2007; Mujis, 2004). Moreover, the ability to translate a questionnaire to an online survey comes with significant benefits during the current ongoing global pandemic, as it allowed to “COVID-proof” the study; as long as the target population has access to the internet, online surveys are particularly robust and flexible in administration and data collection. As such, the current study aimed to conduct a correlational, cross-sectional investigation (Gall et.al., 2007), and tailored design survey method was be used to recruit participants (Dillman et.al., 2014).

An attempt to obtain complementary qualitative data was made through inviting participants to answer two open-ended questions, with the hope to gain a nuanced understanding of personal experience of burnout within the international context.

2.2. MEASURES USED

2.2.1. Demographics

A demographic questionnaire was developed to collect information on participants in the study. Age, gender, geographical region, role and responsibilities, type of school, caseload, and years of experience as school counsellor were all taken into account. In addition, to examine role ambiguity, the participants were asked to state whether their school allowed specific time to implement the counselling curriculum, and whether they felt that other responsibilities interfered with core counselling duties.

Participants were also asked to select areas of work in which they were involved (e.g. university guidance, safeguarding). An open question was included at the end of the survey to allow participants to leave any comments, and/or give more context to their answers.

2.2.2. Counselor Burnout Inventory

The Counselor Burnout Inventory (CBI; Lee et.al., 2010) was utilised to measure counsellors' level of burnout. CBI is a 20-item self-report scale, on a 5-point Likert-type scale (ranging from 1 = "never true" to 5 = "always true"). CBI assesses burnout in five subscales of: exhaustion, incompetence, negative work environment, devaluing client, and deterioration in personal life. The total score can range from 20 to 100, with higher scores indicating higher levels of experienced burnout.

Though Maslach's Burnout Inventory is a robust instrument in measuring burnout in general and caregiver populations (MBI; Maslach and Jackson, 1986), CBI was developed to address and reflect nuances specific to the nature of a therapeutic relationship (Lee et. al., 2010). Studies on the validity and reliability of CBI determined that the measure upheld in relation with MBI (Gnilka et.al., 2015; Lee, et.al., 2007). It was therefore selected to be used as a reliable measure to assess perceived burnout in school counsellors working internationally. Permission of use was obtained from the creator of the measure.

2.2.3. Job Satisfaction Survey

The Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS; Spector, 1985) was utilised to assess perceived job satisfaction within an organisation.

JSS is a 36-item self-report scale, on a 6-point Likert-type scale (ranging from 1 = "disagree very much" to 6 = "agree very much"). JSS includes negatively worded items, which are required to be reverse scored prior to analysis. Total score is calculated by summing all items, with possible ranges from 36 to 216; low ranges reflect high levels of dissatisfaction, and higher ranges represent satisfied workers (Spector, 1997).

JSS attempts to assess job satisfaction through nine subscales: pay, promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, operating conditions, co-workers, nature of work, and communication. In order to address the research questions in this study, total scores for each subscale were also calculated.

Originally developed for use in human service organizations, the high reliability and construct validity rates of JSS has been proven to be applicable for use in all organizations (Spector, 1997). JSS has been established as a quality measure of factors relating to job satisfaction and has been widely used in general organisations as well as among therapeutic and educational professionals, such as mental health support workers, child welfare workers, and school principals (van Saane et.al., 2003), and has been deemed to be the most robust tool in measuring job satisfaction (Spector, 1997).

2.2.4. Quantitative Workload Inventory

The Quantitative Workload Inventory (QWI; Spector and Jex, 1998), was used to measure the quantity of work required to be completed in a job. QWI is a five item self-report scale, on a 5-point Likert-type scale (ranging from 1 – “less than once per month or never” to 5 – “several times per day”). The total score can range from 5 to 25, with higher total scores indicating higher level of workload. QWI reported an average level of inter-reliability across 15 studies (Spector and Jex, 1998); it was therefore included in the study as a suitable measure of perceived workload in a job, as it may help detect high levels of stress when scored highly on the measure. Since role ambiguity and increasing job demands in school counselling communities have been linked to job dissatisfaction (Bryant and Constantine, 2006), workload was therefore included in the current study.

QWI was utilised to assess perceived workload and due to it being a shorter in length measure, it was considered that it would not overwhelm the participants.

2.2.5. Turnover Intentions Scale

The Turnover Intentions Scale (TIS; Michaels and Spector, 1982) was utilised to assess turnover intentions. It is a three-item self-report instrument, on a 5-point Likert-type scale (ranging from 1 = “strongly disagree” to 5 = strongly agree”). The total score can range from 3 to 15, with higher total scores indicating higher intention of leaving the current job. This three-item scale yielded high reliability and validity in significantly predicting turnover (Michaels and Spector, 1982), and was therefore included in the study as a reliable indicator of turnover intentions. This measure is particularly pertinent to this study as reported annual staff turnover in international schools is relatively high, with normal operational annual turnover rate at 30% in the first decade of 2000s (Bunnell; 2014; Mancuso et.al., 2010; Odland and Ruzicka, 2009). There are no reliable recent reports and percentages fluctuate based on school and region (Roberts et.al., 2010; Desroches, 2013), however, with the increasing number of international schools (Reeves and Wigford, 2008; Mancuso et.al., 2010), the projection may even be higher in the current conditions.

Similarly to QWI, TIS is a short and reliable measure (Michaels and Spector, 1982), and was utilised in this study in order to minimise the number of questions the participants had to respond to, while still yielding valid results.

JSS, QWI, and TIS are all available free of charge for non-commercial use via *paulspector.com*, in exchange for sharing the results of the study with the instrument developer, Dr. Paul Spector at University of South Florida.

2.3. PARTICIPANTS AND SAMPLING

The advert for the study was posted on closed member networks which cater to school counsellor educators working internationally: International School Counseling Association (ISCA), and International Association for Admission Counseling (IACAC). An invitation email was sent out to members of those networks, and the advert for the study was also posted in the ISCA monthly newsletters in December 2020 and January 2021. Therefore, all participants in this study were registered members with at least one of the organisations. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary.

G*Power 3.1 software package was utilised to determine the minimum sample size required for the results to be statistically representative (Faul et.al, 2009). To do this, linear multiple regression analysis was selected, with an assumption of moderate effect size of 0.15, (alpha) error probability of 0.05, and power of 0.80 (Cohen, 1988, 1992; Cohen et.al., 2007). The results determined that it was necessary to include at least 43 participants as the minimum suitable sample.

It was expected that responses would be received from the more engaged members in international schools that place value on the school counselling role. It was therefore also expected that a reasonable number of individuals working in schools operating internationally would not be exposed to the survey.

2.4. ETHICAL ISSUES

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Ethics Board Committee at the University of Aberdeen (please refer to the Masters' Ethical Approval Form for a detailed outline of ethical considerations for this project).

In developing the study and research questions, decisions with regard to ethical conduct were made in line with ethical guidelines defined in the Ethical Guidelines for Educational Research (2018) and Social Research Association (SRA) Ethical Guidelines (2003). In addition, ethical codes from different countries were also considered: for example, the American School Counselor Association's Code of Ethics (2014), considered a "gold" standard among some international communities (Brown, 2000). Microsoft Office Forms were utilised to develop the survey and collect anonymous responses from participants.

In considering potential harm to participants that would come through taking part in this study, it was anticipated that participating would involve no to low risk, with no to minimal emotional distress, and none beyond levels encountered in day-to-day life. At no point were the participants asked to disclose their name, name of their school, or any other sensitive personal information. Anonymity and confidentiality was assured, and no responses could be traced back to a particular school or individual. Nevertheless, a paragraph was embedded in the informed consent in order to address

potential risk, stating that should the participant experience emotional distress during or after completion of the questionnaire, they were encouraged to seek psychological support (such as counselling).

Participants were also given the opportunity to withdraw from the study at any point, including once the survey had been completed and submitted. At the end of the survey participants were invited to enter a personal code word, key phrase or a random identification number, which they could use to contact the researcher and withdraw their responses from the data pool.

2.5. PROCEDURE

The researcher contacted the ISCA and IACAC organisations with the details of the study and received permission to send invitations via email to members of the organisation. The ISCA team had also graciously offered to post the details of the study with a link to the survey in their monthly newsletter in December 2020 and January 2021.

As a member of the ISCA and IACAC organisations, the researcher already had access to the member directory, with email and contact information for all registered members. Emails with a voluntary invitation to participate in the study were sent to the total of 884 international school counsellors registered with ISCA and IACAC. The invitation email contained a short paragraph with information on the study, and a link to the survey. The link then took the participants to the informed consent page, which informed them of the time it would take to complete the survey (approximately 10-15 minutes), the purpose of the study, what the information gathered would be used for, and how it would be stored. Participants were assured of anonymity and confidentiality, and that they had the right to withdraw at any time. Participants then had an option to close the survey window if they did not wish to participate, or to select “I Agree” if they were happy to continue. Once the participants submitted the consent form by checking “I Agree” and clicking the ‘*Next*’ button, they were taken to the instruments used in the study, which were divided in four sections: 1. Demographics, 2. Counselor Burnout Inventory, 3. Job Satisfaction Survey, and 4. Quantitative Workload Inventory and

Turnover Intentions Scale combined. Upon completion, the participants were thanked for completing the survey and were prompted to enter a unique identifier (word, phrase, or a number sequence), which would allow them to withdraw their responses from the data pool. No monetary or voucher incentives were offered for participation in the study.

A total of 884 of emails were sent, with 46 emails returning undelivered due to email addresses being invalid, making the total number of potential recipients 838 ($N = 838$). The total number of responses received was 158 ($N = 158$).

Completed responses were downloaded through Microsoft Office 365 Forms in the Excel spreadsheet format and kept in a password-protected folder on an encrypted external hard-drive accessed only by the researcher. The data in the spreadsheet was then examined and open-ended questions were collected into a separate Word document, which was then saved in the same password-protected folder. All numerical data was imported from the Excel file into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 26, IBM Corp; 2019).

2.6. DATA ANALYSIS

All analysis was completed through SPSS and Excel on a password protected computer. SPSS26 (IBM Corp, 2019) was used to produce simple descriptive statistics to provide an overview of data collected. Correlational analysis, multiple analysis of variance, and hierarchical regression analysis were utilised to test the hypotheses of the two research questions in relation to burnout and turnover intentions, and its strength in relation to each variable.

Frequency tables were produced to reflect all categorical variables (Dimitrov, 2009) ([Table 1](#)). Mean and standard deviation was reported for the single scale variable *caseload* ([Table 2](#)). Microsoft Office Excel and SPSS chart builder (IBM Corp, 2019) were used to produce graphs to help visualise the data.

CHAPTER 3: FINDINGS

3.1. QUALITATIVE DATA

Qualitative data was gathered through open questions to give participants an opportunity to share particulars relating to their personal situation and experience. Though not analysed in depth, qualitative answers were used to complement quantitative findings where applicable to help provide greater insight.

3.2 DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

Demographic information was collected from each participant, with descriptive statistics including all predictor variables (categorical and continuous); criterion variable frequencies and means and standard deviations were reported in the tables below.

	N	% of Sample
Age		
20-29	10	6.3
30-39	46	29.1
40-49	66	41.8
50-59	27	17.1
60+	9	5.7
Gender		
Male	45	28.5
Female	111	70.3
Prefer not to say	2	1.3
Region		
Africa, Sub Saharan	13	8.2
Caribbean, Central America, and Mexico	12	7.6

East Asia	33	20.9
Europe	29	18.4
Middle East and North Africa	17	10.8
South America	16	10.1
South and Central Asia	13	8.2
Southeast Asia and Oceania	25	15.8
Type of school		
Public	5	3.2
Private	153	96.8
Years of experience as school or university guidance counsellor		
Under 3 Years	24	15.2
3-10 Years	65	41.1
10+ Years	69	43.7
Interference of other responsibilities with core counselling duties		
Not at All	11	7.0
Sometimes	28	17.7
Somewhat Often	53	33.5
Several Times a Week	35	22.2
On a daily basis	31	19.6
Role and responsibilities (participants could select multiple options)		
High School	98	62
Middle School	49	31
Elementary School	34	21.5
University Guidance	76	48.1
Child Protection and Safeguarding	47	29.7
Teaching	21	13.3
Dean of Students	5	3.2
Director of Student Support	8	5.1
Does the school timetable allow sufficient time to run counselling programmes		
Yes	55	34.8
No	84	53.2
Other	19	12

Table 1: Demographic Data for Categorical Predictor Variables ($n = 158$)

	Mean	Standard Deviation
Caseload	198	180

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for Continuous Predictor Variable ($n = 158$)

3.2.1. Age

Demographic information was collected on each participant. The majority identified as being in their 40s ($n = 66, 41.7\%$). The second highest age demographic identified as being in their 30s ($n = 46, 29.1\%$). The lowest age demographic were participants identifying as being 60+ ($n = 9, 5.7\%$). See [Table 1](#) and [Figure 1](#) for age group distributions.

Figure 1: Age Group Frequency Graph ($n = 158$)

3.2.2. Gender

As outlined in [Table 1](#) and [Figure 2](#), there were more female participants ($n = 111, 70.3\%$), than male participants ($n = 45, 28.5\%$), and two participants ($n = 2, 1.3\%$) preferred not to disclose their gender identity.

Figure 2: Gender Distribution Chart ($n = 158$)

3.2.3. Region

[Table 1](#) and [Figure 3](#) show that the majority of participants in the current sample were based in East Asia ($n = 33, 20.9\%$), Europe ($n = 29, 18.4\%$), and Southeast Asia and Oceania ($n = 25, 15.8\%$). Participation from the other five regions was more or less evenly distributed, ranging from 12-17 people (7.6%-10.8%).

Canada and the United States yielded no answers. This could be explained by the fact that the survey was aimed at school counsellor educators based “internationally”, and members of international organisations. It can be argued that most participants in schools in Canada and the United States belong to national organisations (e.g. NACAC⁵), rather than international.

⁵ United States based National Association for College Admission Counseling (NACAC)

Figure 3: Breakdown of participants by geographical location ($n = 158$)

3.2.4. Type of School

Upon examination of the results, it was discovered that only 5 (3.2%) participants were based in public schools (Table 1). This could be explained by international schools usually catering to international expat communities, and largely operating as private corporate entities (Creemers et.al., 2002; James and Sheppard, 2014).

Nevertheless, since the number was too small to obtain any significant value when conducting statistical analysis, the type of school variable was excluded from further analysis.

3.2.5. Years of Experience

Table 1 and Figure 4 show that the majority of participants in the current study identified as having over 3 years of experience in the school counselling field. Sixty nine (43.7%) participants stated over ten years' experience, and sixty five people stated between three and ten years (41.1%). Only twenty four people stated that they had under three years of experience (15.2%).

Figure 4: Years of experience as school or university guidance counsellor ($n = 158$)

3.2.6. Interference of Other Responsibilities

Participants were asked whether they thought that their non-counselling responsibilities (e.g. lunch duty, supervision, scheduling; Bardhoshi et.al., 2014; Gysbers and Henderson, 2001) interfered with their core counselling duties. Eleven (7%) participants stated ‘Not At All’; the majority ($n = 53$, 33.5%) identified the interference as ‘Somewhat Often’; the second largest ($n = 35$, 22.2%) identified the interference as “Several Times a Week; and the third largest ($n = 31$, 19.6%) identified interference “On a Daily Basis” (Table 1). It can therefore be argued that most participants in the current sample perceive the interference of non-counselling duties with their core responsibilities as a moderate to high degree.

3.2.7. Adequate Time for Counselling Curriculum

Participants were asked whether the school timetable allows sufficient time to implement specialised counselling or university guidance curriculum. The majority ($n = 84$, 53.2%) declared that their school does not allow sufficient time for implementation (Table 1).

Twelve participants said “Other”, which allowed them to enter a response to elaborate. The responses varied based on context: for example, one participant stated that they had built-in time for grades 7 and 8, but not for grade 9. Several responses echoed that during the pandemic, blended or online learning made scheduling challenging and they did not have sufficient built-in time for a counselling curriculum.

3.2.8. *Role and Responsibilities*

Participants were asked to identify the primary setting in which they worked. They were able to select multiple responses, which was intended to account for role ambiguity and allow insight into the extra responsibilities they are required to undertake. The majority stated that they worked in the high school setting ($n = 98$, 62% of cases). The second largest number worked in university guidance ($n = 76$, 48.1%). See Table 3 for further breakdown.

	Responses		Percent of Cases
	N	Percent	
High School	98	29.0%	62.0%
Middle School	49	14.5%	31.0%
Elementary School	34	10.1%	21.5%
University Guidance	76	22.5%	48.1%
Child Protection and Safeguarding	47	13.9%	29.7%
Teaching	21	6.2%	13.3%
Dean of Students	5	1.5%	3.2%
Director of Student Support	8	2.4%	5.1%
Total	338	100.0%	213.9%

Table 3: Breakdown of primary operational setting and responsibilities counsellors engaged in ($n = 158$)

3.2.9. *Caseload*

Demographic data was collected for the number of students on each counsellor’s caseload. The number of students per counsellor ranged from 20 to 800; [Table 2](#) reports a mean score of 198, with a standard deviation of 180. The participants in the current study therefore had a mean student per counsellor ratio of 198:1.

3.3. STATISTICAL ANALYSES

3.3.1. Reliability of Measures

Descriptive statistics were calculated for all measures implemented to test the hypothesis for research questions one and two, in addressing predictability of variables on school counsellor burnout in international settings. Total scores were calculated for QWI, TIS, JSS and CBI; subscales on pay, promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, operating conditions, co-workers, nature of work, and communication were separated and calculated for JSS, and exhaustion, incompetence, negative work environment, devaluing client, and deterioration in personal life subscales were additionally calculated for CBI.

All assumptions relevant to this study were tested and achieved for JSS, CBI, TIS, and QWI; no multicollinearity, multivariate normality, and homoscedasticity (Hair et.al., 2018). No outliers were identified that could potentially influence the outcomes, and all assumptions were met for all measures (Dimitrov, 2009; Hair et.al., 2018).

Coefficient alphas were calculated to check for internal consistency reliability of all measures and their subscales (Cronbach, 1951; Dimitrov, 2009). All measures reported high internal consistency reliability (Table 4), suggesting validity of all measures used in the study. In addition, coefficient alphas for subscales in JSS and CBI were calculated to test for internal reliability of each subscale, reporting internal consistency reliability (Table 5).

Measure	Score Range	Mean	SD	A
JSS	49 – 204	132.48	31.57	.94
CBI	26 - 87	50.37	12.72	.92
QWI	6 - 25	17.46	4.88	.89
TIS	3 - 15	10.17	5.22	.88

Table 4: Quality of measures ($n = 158$)

Measure	Mean	SD	A
JSS (subscale score range: 4 - 24)			
Pay	13.38	5.45	.84
Promotion	11.37	4.80	.84

Supervision	17.56	5.45	.89
Fringe Benefits	14.01	5.41	.85
Contingent Rewards	14.57	5.06	.84
Operating Conditions	12.44	4.24	.70
Co-workers	16.87	4.69	.81
Nature of Work	18.70	4.13	.84
Communication	13.59	5.06	.83
CBI (subscale score range 4 – 20)			
Exhaustion	13.11	3.58	.89
Incompetence	9.59	3.06	.80
Negative Work Environment	10.93	4.11	.89
Devaluing Client	5.95	2.17	.81
Deterioration to Personal Life	10.76	3.91	.88

Table 5: Quality of JSS and CBI subscale measures ($n = 158$)

3.3.2. JSS

Coefficient alphas were calculated to check for internal consistency reliability of the Job Satisfaction Survey. The original analysis of the 36 items for the JSS completed by Spector yielded a coefficient alpha of .91 (Spector, 1985). The internal consistency reliability of the measure with the current sample obtained a value of .94. The range of scores for the current sample ranged from 49 to 204, with a mean score of 132.48 and standard deviation of 31.57. The mean score of 132.48 reveals overall ambivalence toward their jobs (scores of 108 to 144, Spector, 1997).

Means and standard deviations were reported for each subscale to identify overall trends in job satisfaction domains in the current sample (Table 5). With the highest possible score of each sub-scale being 24, Spector (1985; 1997) suggests that score ranges between 4-12 reflect dissatisfaction, 12–16 reflect ambivalence, and 16–24 reflect overall satisfaction within each domain.

The domain of promotion and opportunities for growth indicated overall dissatisfaction in the current sample with the mean score of 11.37 ($SD = 4.80$). Varied levels of ambivalence were reported for operating conditions ($M = 12.44$, $SD = 4.24$), communication ($M = 13.59$, $SD = 5.06$), pay ($M = 13.38$, $SD = 5.45$), fringe benefits ($M = 14.04$, $SD = 5.41$), and contingent rewards ($M = 14.57$, $SD = 5.06$) subscales.

Supervision ($M = 17.56$, $SD = 5.45$), co-workers ($M = 16.87$, $SD = 4.69$), and nature of work ($M = 18.70$, $SD = 4.13$) subscale scores effectively suggest that in the

current sample, the majority of the participants were relatively satisfied with supervision, interactions with co-workers, and job tasks themselves.

3.3.3. CBI

Coefficient alphas were calculated to check for internal consistency reliability of the Counselor Burnout Inventory. The original analysis of the 20 items for the CBI completed by Lee et al. yielded a coefficient alpha of .88 (Lee et.al., 2007); repeated analysis of aggregated internal consistency yielded a coefficient alpha of .90 (Bardhoshi et.al, 2019). The internal consistency reliability of the measure with the current sample obtained a value of .92. The range of scores for the current sample was 26-87, with a mean of 50.37 and standard deviation of 12.72. The mean of 50.37 reveals that participants in the current sample experience moderate to high levels of burnout.

Means and standard deviations were reported for each subscale to identify overall trends in perception of counsellor burnout domains in the current sample ([Table 5](#)). The exhaustion subscale revealed the highest mean score of 13.11 (SD = 3.58), suggesting a relatively high level of reported exhaustion. Moderate levels of burnout were reported within the incompetence (M = 9.59, SD = 3.06), negative work environment (M = 10.93, SD = 4.11), and deterioration to personal life (M = 10.76, SD = 3.91) domains. While devaluing client was revealed to be the lowest contributor to burnout (M = 5.95, SD = 2.17).

3.4. CORRELATIONS

Correlations were assessed in order to provide an overview of the strength of the relationship between tested variables, as well as the direction of said relationship. Doing so also assists researchers in testing for multicollinearity issues (Blalock, 1963). There were no concerns of multicollinearity upon initial analysis, as no correlation exceeded .9 value (Blalock, 1963).

Upon exclusion of the ‘type of school’ variable, the total of twenty-six variables were included in the current study, and several Pearson’s correlational analyses were completed to determine significant interactions between various combinations of pairs of variables and their impact on burnout and turnover intentions.

Due to the large number of variables, this resulted in numerous tests, therefore only significant interactions, set with alpha at 0.05 (Cohen, 1992) were reported in the findings. Significant and non-significant correlations are discussed. Table 5 below presents a brief summary of significant correlations.

Predictor Variable	Criterion Variable	Correlation (<i>r</i>)
Age	Burnout	-.249
Years of Experience	Burnout	-.239
Interference of other duties	Burnout	.443
Overall Job Satisfaction	Burnout	-.729
Workload	Burnout	.464
Pay	Burnout	-.315
Promotion	Burnout	-.401
Supervision	Burnout	-.543
Fringe Benefits	Burnout	-.337
Contingent Rewards	Burnout	-.607
Operating Conditions	Burnout	-.627
Co-workers	Burnout	-.604
Nature of Work	Burnout	-.656
Communication	Burnout	-.649
Workload	Burnout	.464
Region	Turnover Intention	.226
Overall Burnout	Turnover Intention	.419
Overall Job Satisfaction	Turnover Intention	-.488
Pay	Turnover Intention	-.250
Promotion	Turnover Intention	-.320
Supervision	Turnover Intention	-.436
Fringe Benefits	Turnover Intention	-.192
Contingent Rewards	Turnover Intention	-.402
Operating Conditions	Turnover Intention	-.354
Co-workers	Turnover Intention	-.335
Nature of Work	Turnover Intention	-.341
Communication	Turnover Intention	-.506
Exhaustion	Turnover Intention	.393
Negative Work Environment	Turnover Intention	.454
Deterioration to Personal Life	Turnover Intention	.329

Table 6: Statistically significant correlations in relation to burnout and turnover intentions ($p < .01$)

3.4.1. Non-Significant Correlations

Several demographic variables did not correlate with criterion variables: region, gender, roles and responsibilities, caseload, and counselling curriculum implementation did not correlate with levels of burnout in the current sample.

Age, gender, years of experience, role and responsibilities, interference of non-counselling duties, counselling curriculum implementation, caseload, incompetence, and deterioration to client relationship (devaluing client), did not produce significant correlations with turnover intentions in the current sample.

3.4.2. Significant Correlations

Significant correlations were further sub-divided into three categories: low, moderate, and high. Low correlations were considered when reported values were between 0.1 and 0.3, moderate between 0.3 and 0.5, and high between 0.5 and 1.0 (Cohen, 1988).

Several variables produced significant correlations in the current sample ([Table 6](#)). The overall JSS scale and all of its subscales showed significant correlations with burnout and turnover intentions, with various degrees of strength. Though overall burnout (CBI) correlated with turnover intentions, most, but not all CBI subscales produced significant correlations with moderate correlational strength (Cohen, 1988).

3.4.2.i. Low Correlations

A number of low strength correlations, with values between 0.1 and 0.3 (Cohen, 1988), were reported.

Burnout was negatively correlated with age ($r = -.249$) and years of experience ($r = -.239$): as participants got older and gained more years of experience, the reported perceived levels of burnout decreased.

Region showed a positive relationship with turnover intentions ($r = .226$), suggesting that some regions play a role in intentions to leave one's job.

Turnover intentions were additionally negatively correlated with pay ($r = -.250$) and fringe benefits ($r = -.192$). As satisfaction with pay and fringe benefits were lower, the intention to leave increased.

3.4.2.ii. Moderate Correlations

A number of moderate strength correlations, of values between 0.3 and 0.5 (Cohen, 1988), were reported.

Overall burnout was positively correlated with turnover intentions ($r = .419$): as levels of burnout increased, the intention to leave the current job also increased. Overall job satisfaction was negatively correlated with turnover intentions ($r = -.488$): as levels of job satisfaction decreased, the intention to leave increased.

Interferences of non-counselling duties with counselling work showed a positive correlation with burnout ($r = .443$). With an increase of extra non-counselling duties, the levels of burnout also increased. Similarly, workload demonstrated a positive relationship with burnout ($r = .464$): with increased workload the levels of burnout also increased.

Burnout was negatively correlated with pay ($r = -.315$), promotion and opportunities for growth ($r = -.401$), and fringe benefits ($r = -.337$), all arguably falling under an umbrella of career growth and remuneration. As satisfaction with pay, benefits, and career opportunities decreased, the levels of burnout increased.

Several JSS subscales reported moderate negative correlations with turnover intentions: promotion ($r = -.320$), supervision ($r = -.436$), contingent rewards ($r = -.402$), operating conditions ($r = -.354$), co-workers ($r = -.335$), and nature of work ($r = -.341$). As satisfaction with opportunities for promotion, contingent rewards, operating conditions, and enjoyment from work decreased, turnover intentions increased. Similarly, as positive relationship with supervisor and co-workers decreased, turnover intentions increased.

3.4.2.iii. High Correlations

Several high strength correlations, of values between 0.5 and 1.0 (Cohen, 1988), were reported in the current sample.

Overall job satisfaction revealed the highest strength negative correlation with burnout ($r = -.729$), suggesting that as levels of job satisfaction decreased, levels of burnout increased.

The remaining JSS subscales showed high negative correlations with burnout: contingent rewards ($r = -.607$), operating conditions ($r = -.627$), co-workers ($r = -.604$), nature of work ($r = -.656$), and communication ($r = -.649$). As satisfaction with rewards and the nature of work decreased, the levels of burnout increased. Similarly, as positive relationship with co-workers decreased, burnout increased. Finally, when levels of satisfaction with communication within the organisation were reported as low, burnout increased.

The highest strength negative correlation for turnover intention was reported within the communication subscale ($r = -.506$). When levels of satisfaction with communication within the organisation were reported as low, the intention to leave current job increased.

3.5. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Several multiple linear regression analyses were conducted to address research questions. Alpha level was set at .05 to determine statistical significance and reduce probability of Type I and Type II errors (deVaus, 2002). All models tested reported the variance inflation factor (VIF) values ranging from 1.115 to 2.714, therefore confirming that there was no multicollinearity and that each variable measured a separate construct (Dimitrov, 2009). Multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the impact of variables on burnout in international school counsellors, with separate analyses to test impact of variables (inclusive of factors of burnout) on turnover intentions among school counsellor educators based internationally.

3.5.1. Hierarchical Regression Analysis

To test the hypotheses of research questions one and two hierarchical regression analysis was used. This allowed for greater control over variables, as it was possible to enter them in separate blocks, which also allowed for testing of mediating relationships (Richardson et.al., 2015).

3.5.1.i. Burnout

To test research question one, hierarchical regression analysis was performed to determine the influence of variables on burnout in international school counsellor educators. Burnout was set as a criterion variable, and the following demographic variables were included as predictor variables during Stage One of the analysis: age, gender, region, years of experience, role and responsibilities, interference of non-counselling duties, counselling curriculum implementation, and caseload. Subscales of JSS and QWI were set as predictor variables at Stage Two of the analysis: pay, promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, quality of work relationships (co-workers), operating conditions, communication, and workload. See Table 15 for results.

Variables	Stage One		Stage Two	
	β	t	β	t
Age	-.16	-2.03*	.09	1.58
Gender	.01	.10	-.07	-1.43
Region	.02	.25	-.06	-1.09
Experience	-.10	-.12	-.11	-1.92
Role	-.06	-.87	.01	.03
Interference	.41	5.64**	.01	.04
Curriculum	-.10	-1.44	-.01	-.14
Caseload	.11	1.49	-.04	-.86
Pay			-.21	-2.68**
Promotion			-.07	-1.06
Supervision			-.07	-1.10
Benefits			-.24	-3.25**
Rewards			-.03	-.33
Co-workers			-.15	-2.21**
Conditions			.11	-1.32
Nature of Work			-.39	-6.38**
Communication			-.16	-2.06*
Workload			.18	2.88**

F Value	6.76**	17.68**
R ²	.27	.66
R ² _{adj}	.27	.43
D-W Coefficient		1.945
VIF Value	1.015 – 2.676	

Table 15: Influence of variables on burnout, hierarchical regression analysis. (*p< 0.05, **p<0.01)

Table 15 demonstrates that demographic variables included in Stage One of the analysis collectively contributed to levels of burnout experienced by school counsellor educators based internationally ($R^2 = .27$, $F(8, 149) = 6.76$, $p < .01$). Demographic variables collectively accounted for 27% of variance in burnout. However, only age ($\beta = -.16$, $p < .05$) and interference of non-counselling duties ($\beta = .41$, $p < .01$) had a significant impact on burnout. Therefore, as the age increased, and interference of non-counselling duties with core counselling duties decreased, the school counsellor educators experienced less burnout.

To test the independent effects of job satisfaction on burnout, subscales of JSS were introduced as variables in Stage Two of the analysis. The results indicated that pay, promotion, supervision, benefits and rewards, relationship with co-workers, working conditions, nature of work, workload, and communication, collectively significantly predicted burnout, and accounted for 66% of variance in burnout. The introduction of the JSS subscales resulted in an additional 43% change in perceived burnout in the current sample ($R^2 = .66$; $R^2_{adj} = .43$, $F(10, 139) = 17.68$, $p < .01$). Pay ($\beta = -.21$, $p < .01$), fringe benefits ($\beta = -.24$, $p < .01$), relationship with co-workers ($\beta = -.15$, $p < .01$), nature of work ($\beta = -.39$, $p < .01$), communication ($\beta = -.39$, $p < .01$), and workload ($\beta = .18$, $p < .01$), all significantly predicted burnout in the current sample. Promotion ($\beta = -.09$, $p > .05$), supervision ($\beta = -.11$, $p > .05$), contingent rewards ($\beta = -.03$, $p > .05$), and operating conditions ($\beta = .11$, $p > .05$) were not strong factors in predicting burnout.

Age and interference of non-counselling duties were significant in predicting burnout during Stage One of the analysis but were offset in influence in Stage Two. The implication of the findings was that lower satisfaction with pay, fewer benefits, worse relationships with colleagues, less satisfaction with the job tasks themselves, worse

inter-school communication, and increased workload resulted in increased burnout regardless of participant's age or impact of non-counselling duties. Job satisfaction emerged as the strongest predictor of counsellor burnout in the current sample.

Based on the results, the null hypothesis of research question one can be rejected, as job satisfaction successfully predicted burnout in the current sample.

3.5.1.ii. Turnover Intentions

To test research question two, hierarchical regression analysis was performed to determine the influence of variables on turnover intentions in international school counsellors. Turnover intention was set as a criterion variable, and the following demographic variables were included as predictor variables during Stage One of the analysis: age, gender, region, years of experience, role and responsibilities, interference of non-counselling duties, counselling curriculum implementation, and caseload. JSS subscales and QWI were set as predictor variables at Stage Two of the analysis to account for environmental variables (job satisfaction): workload, pay, promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, quality of work relationships (co-workers), operating conditions, and communication. Finally, subscales of CBI were set as predictor variables at Stage Three of the analysis to account for psychological factors (burnout): exhaustion, incompetence, negative work environment, devaluing client, and deterioration to personal life. Results reported in Table 16.

Variables	Stage One		Stage Two		Stage Three	
	β	t	β	t	β	t
Age	-.11	-1.31	.03	.31	.01	.13
Gender	.05	.62	.031	.44	.06	.77
Region	.22	2.94**	.18	2.53**	.19	2.59**
Experience	.00	.04	-.01	-.07	-.01	-.08
Role	-.01	-.17	.03	.37	.03	.42
Interference	.35	4.57**	.16	1.82	.17	1.82
Curriculum	.07	.99	.14	1.96	.14	2.00*
Caseload	-.00	-.01	-.08	-1.15	-.07	-.94
Pay			-.04	-.38	-.05	-.44
Promotion			-.06	-.69	-.06	-.58
Supervision			-.16	-1.68	-.16	-1.49
Benefits			.01	.07	-.02	.21
Rewards			-.07	-.53	-.07	-.49
Co-workers			.09	.96	.11	1.12
Conditions			.21	1.88	-.23	-1.99*

Nature of Work		-.07	-.86	-.07	-.68
Communication		-.36	-3.32**	-.33	-2.87**
Workload		.19	2.06*	.16	1.59
Exhaustion				.19	1.45
Incompetence				-.00	-.04
Negative Env.				.06	.43
Devaluing Client				-.05	-.51
Deterioration				-.12	-1.01
F Value	4.47**		4.89**		3.92**
R ²	.19		.39		.40
R ² _{adj}	.15		.31		.30
D-W Coefficient					2.097
VIF Value	1.032 –				
	2.714				

Table 16: Influence of variables on turnover intentions, hierarchical regression analysis (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$)

Table 16 shows that demographic variables included in Step One of the analysis collectively contributed to turnover intentions in the current sample ($R^2 = .19$, $F(8, 149) = 4.47$, $p < .01$). Demographic variables collectively accounted for 19% of variance in turnover intentions. However, only region ($\beta = .22$, $p < .01$) and interference of non-counselling duties ($\beta = .35$, $p < .01$) emerged as significant factors impacting turnover intentions. Therefore, the region participants were based in and higher interference of non-counselling duties with core responsibilities indicated an increase in turnover intentions in the current sample.

To test the effects of job satisfaction on turnover intentions, subscales of JSS and QWI were introduced as variables at Stage Two of the analysis. The results indicated that pay, promotion, supervision, benefits and rewards, co-workers, working conditions, nature of work, workload, and communication, collectively significantly predicted turnover intentions in the current sample and accounted for 39% of variance in burnout. The introduction of the JSS subscales and QWI resulted in an additional 20% change in turnover intentions ($R^2 = .39$; $R^2_{adj} = .31$, $F(10, 139) = 4.89$, $p < .01$). Region ($\beta = .18$, $p < .01$), workload ($\beta = 2.06$, $p < .05$), and communication ($\beta = -.36$, $p < .01$), significantly predicted turnover intentions in the current sample. While pay ($\beta = -.04$, $p > .05$), promotion ($\beta = -.06$, $p > .05$), supervision ($\beta = -.16$, $p > .05$), fringe benefits ($\beta = .01$, $p > .05$), contingent rewards ($\beta = -.07$, $p > .05$), operating conditions

($\beta = .21, p > .05$), and nature of work ($\beta = -.07, p > .05$), were not strong factors in predicting turnover. Interference of non-counselling duties was a significant factor during Stage One, but was offset in influence in Stage Two. These results suggest that region participants were based in, worse perception of inter-school communication, and higher workload increased turnover intentions in the current sample.

To test the effects of burnout on turnover intentions, subscales of CBI were introduced as variables during Stage Three of the analysis. The results indicated that exhaustion, incompetence, negative work environment, devaluing client, and deterioration to personal life all collectively significantly predicted turnover intentions in the current sample and accounted for 40% of variance. The introduction of the CBI subscales resulted in an additional 1% change in turnover intentions in the current sample ($R^2 = .40$; $R^2_{\text{adj}} = .30, F(5, 134) = 3.92, p < .01$). Region ($\beta = .19, p < .01$), curriculum implementation ($\beta = .14, p < .05$), operating conditions ($\beta = -.23, p < .05$), and communication ($\beta = -.33, p < .01$) all significantly predicted turnover intentions. None of the subscales of burnout were strong predictors of turnover intentions in the current sample: exhaustion ($\beta = .19, p > .05$), incompetence ($\beta = -.00, p > .05$), devaluing client ($\beta = -.05, p > .05$), negative work environment ($\beta = .06, p > .05$), and deterioration of personal life ($\beta = -.12, p > .05$). Workload was a significant factor in Stage Two of the analysis but was offset in influence during Stage Three. However, curriculum implementation and operating conditions emerged as significant predictors of turnover intentions when interacting with all other variables. These results suggest that region participants were based in, lack of time to implement counselling curriculum, worse levels of perceived intra-school communication, and worse perception of operating conditions increased turnover intentions in the current sample.

3.5.2. Regional Statistics for Turnover Intentions

To test hypotheses 3(a) and 3(b) of research question three, multiple regression analysis was conducted to test influence of factors on turnover intentions broken down by region. As seen in [Table 16](#), region emerged as a considerably significant factor ($R^2 = .40$; $F(5, 134) = 3.92, \beta = .19, p < .01$) influencing turnover intentions in the current

sample. Significance of region as a factor remained constant in all three stages of testing.

As seen in the results from the hierarchical regression model, the only variables that remained constant were region and communication (domain of job satisfaction), with interference of other duties showing significance in relation to demographics but becoming mediated once additional factors of job satisfaction and burnout were introduced to the model. Workload showed significance in relation to demographics and job satisfaction before burnout was introduced in the final step of the model. Multiple linear regression analyses were therefore completed to test whether there were significant regional differences in role and expectations, job satisfaction, workload, and burnout in relation to turnover intentions.

Due to this analysis generating a large amount of data, only the significant findings were reported. Critical F values were calculated for each region to additionally test for relationship significance.

<i>Region</i>	<i>Variable</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>VIF</i>	<i>Critical F value</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>R</i> ²	<i>R</i> ² _{adj}
<i>Africa Sub Saharan</i>	Deterioration to personal life	1.01	2.90*	2.791	2.143	4.791	.85	.75
	Role	1.80	2.70*	3.764		2.439	.67	.20
<i>Caribbean, Central America and Mexico</i>	Interference of other duties	.68	2.456*	1.383	2.094	2.723	.61	.39
	Communication	-.75	-2.891**	2.811	1.837	2.206	.47	.23
<i>Europe</i>	Exhaustion	.46	2.319*	2.301		6.489	.55	.46
	Incompetence	.55	3.501*	1.776				
	Role	-.56	-2.086*	2.521		2.298	.30	.10
	Exhaustion	.88	3.908**	2.753	1.924	7.877	.79	.75
	Negative Work Environment	.53	2.807*	3.993				
	Deterioration to Personal Life	-.55	-2.147*	1.840				
	Interference of other responsibilities	.52	3.028*	1.172		3.232	.35	.24
<i>Middle East and North Africa</i>	Role	.83	2.624*	1.366	2.456	2.706	.53	.25
<i>South America</i>	Exhaustion	-.91	-2.283*	3.190	2.523	4.595	.69	.55
	Negative Work Environment	1.26	4.059*	3.178				
	Role	.73	2.928*	1.585		2.543	.69	.42

<i>South and Central Asia</i>	Workload	.46	5.014*	2.260	2.913	6.293	.79	.86
<i>Southeast Asia and Oceania</i>	Role	.87	-3.85**	1.897	2.039	2.829	.78	.36

Table 17. Influence of variables on turnover intentions, regional breakdown (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$)

Table 17 represents significant factors that influence turnover intentions broken down by region. All regions reported significant results. Africa, Sub Saharan region reported that deterioration to personal life ($\beta = 1.01, p < .05$) and role ($\beta = 1.80, p < .05$), were the strongest factors in significantly influencing turnover intention. In the Caribbean, Central America and Mexico, interference of non-counselling duties with core counselling responsibilities, emerged as the sole significant factor in predicting turnover intentions ($\beta = .68, p < .05$). East Asia reported several significant factors: communication ($\beta = -.75, p < .01$), exhaustion ($\beta = .46, p < .05$), incompetence ($\beta = .55, p < .05$), and role ($\beta = -.56, p < .05$). Europe also reported significant influence of CBI subscale factors on turnover intentions: exhaustion ($\beta = .88, p < .01$), negative work environment ($\beta = .53, p < .05$), deterioration to personal life ($\beta = -.55, p < .05$), and interference of non-counselling duties with counselling responsibilities ($\beta = .52, p < .05$). The Middle East and North Africa reported significance of role ($\beta = .83, p < .05$). South America revealed that exhaustion ($\beta = -.91, p < .05$), negative work environment ($\beta = 1.26, p < .05$), and role ($\beta = .73, p < .05$) all had significant influence on turnover intentions. Central Asia showed that workload ($\beta = .46, p < .05$) was a significant factor in the region. Finally, for the Southeast Asia and Oceania region, role and responsibilities emerged significant in predicting turnover intentions ($\beta = .87, p < .01$).

3.5.3. Regional Statistics for Counsellor Burnout

Though region was not significant in initially predicting burnout in the current sample, since it emerged as a consistently significant variable in influencing turnover intentions, it was pertinent to investigate whether there were any significant findings that emerged within different regions. Multiple regression analysis was performed to

test this, and critical F values were additionally calculated to test the significance of the relationship. Only statistically significant relationships were reported (Table 18).

<i>Region</i>	<i>Variable</i>	<i>beta</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>VIF</i>	<i>Critical F value</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>R²</i>	<i>ΔR²</i>
<i>Africa, Sub Saharan</i>	Co-workers	.92	3.29*	3.157	3.259	7.339	.74	.64
	Pay	.49	2.43*	3.013	1.884	8.218	.79	.69
<i>East Asia</i>	Nature of Work	-.56	-3.57**	2.551				
	Fringe Benefits	-.42	-2.28*	3.486				
<i>Europe</i>	Nature of Work	-.32	-2.16*	1.823	1.986	10.016	.85	.76
	Workload	.49	2.90*	3.383				
	Contingent Rewards	-.50	-2.53*	2.621				
	Interference of other duties	.68	4.27**	1.286		4.933	.57	.46
<i>South America</i>	Caseload	.78	3.53*	2.078	2.587	5.613	.78	.64
	Interference of other duties	.58	3.33*	1.294				

Table 18: Influence of variables on burnout, regional breakdown (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$)

Table 18 shows that there were indeed significant relationships within specific regions influencing burnout. Three geographical regions that emerged in this analysis were Africa, Sub Saharan, East Asia and Europe. Subscales of JSS, co-workers ($\beta = .92$, $p < .05$), which assessed relationships with colleagues, emerged as a significant factor in perceived burnout for Africa, Sub Saharan region. Subscales of JSS, pay ($\beta = .49$, $p < .05$), nature of work ($\beta = -.56$, $p < .01$), and fringe benefits ($\beta = -.42$, $p < .05$) had significant impact on burnout in East Asia, with nature of work emerging as the strongest predictor. Subscales of JSS, nature of work ($\beta = -.32$, $p < .05$), contingent rewards ($\beta = -.50$, $p < .05$), workload ($\beta = .49$, $p < .05$), and interference of other duties ($\beta = .68$, $p < .01$), all emerged as significant predictors of burnout in Europe, with interference of non-counselling duties being significantly strongest. For South America, caseload ($\beta = .78$, $p < .05$), and interference of other duties ($\beta = .58$, $p < .05$), were most significant factors in predicting burnout.

CHAPTER 4: DISCUSSION

Findings showed several statistically significant correlations between variables in the current study. Moreover, findings showed significance in set demographic, environmental (JSS and QWI), and psychological (CBI) predictor variables in explaining variance for the criterion variables (burnout and turnover intentions). Moreover, significant factors emerged particular to each region to explain burnout and turnover intentions in the current sample, therefore supporting the alternative hypothesis for all research questions tested in this study.

When discussing the findings, it is important to recognise particulars of the sample to consider the context of the current study.

4.1. DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

The majority of the participants were women, in their 40s, with over ten years of experience in school counselling, working with high school students and/or with a focus in on university guidance, with a student to counsellor ratio of 198:1, based in private schools overseas. Most were based in three geographical regions; Europe, East Asia, and Southeast Asia and Oceania. On average, participants expressed that their school does not allow sufficient time for implementation of the counselling curriculum, and interference of non-counselling duties with core counselling responsibilities was classed as “somewhat often”. Participants reported overall ambivalence toward their jobs, and experienced moderate to high levels of burnout.

4.2. RESEARCH QUESTION ONE: Factors influencing burnout in international school and university guidance counsellors.

Null hypothesis 1 was rejected for research question one, as a number of statistically significant correlations emerged as factors explaining burnout in the current sample. Additional regression analysis demonstrated statistical significance in explaining the predictive value of several demographic and environmental factors that were tested.

4.2.1. Age and Experience

Out of demographic factors tested, age and years of experience were negatively correlated with perceived levels of burnout, which implies that older, more experienced professionals had lower reported levels of burnout, while early career professionals experienced higher levels of burnout.

This is consistent with previous research; Maslach argued that early career professionals experience more burnout due to their “lack of experience” (Cummings and Nall, 1982; Maslach, 2001). The findings of the current study highlight the need for change in current practice to meet the needs of young professionals starting out with their school counselling careers.

Upon closer examination, age remained a significant factor in predicting burnout when tested against other demographic factors, however, once additional job satisfaction elements were introduced, the significance of age was offset, suggesting that contentedness with areas of one’s job may offset the lack of experience in early career professionals.

This construct has been explored and is relatively consistent with the idea that occupation-related factors such as supervision and positive relationships with co-workers may act as a buffer against burnout in early career professionals (Baggerly and Osborn, 2006; Wachter et al., 2008).

Supervision did not emerge as a significant predictor in burnout in the current sample. This may be due to the fact that vast majority of participants were in their 40s, with over 10 years of experience: it can be assumed that they are mid-career professionals who may already be familiar with various aspects and demands of their jobs and are not necessarily in need of further supervision or training. Moreover, this factor was highlighted by respondents through an open question:

“Supervision is a huge element for me. I am new to the counseling [sic] and college counselling role, and I have very little support. My supervisor knows nothing of what I do [...] I feel like there is a lot of pressure on me, but I receive no support.” (Participant 153, Lines 2-5)

“My department supervisor is not very effective and tends to not stay up to date within the field.” (Participant 126, Lines 3-4)

Previous research examined the role of consultation (defined as a system of service and support in problem solving among colleagues (Dollarhide and Saginak, 2012; Fye et.al., 2020)) in school counsellors, and found that it may not only serve as an alternative to supervision, but also safeguard against burnout (Moyer, 2011; Wilkerson and Bellini, 2006) particularly when direct supervision was not a viable option (Lawson, 2007). It had also been suggested that early career professionals may engage in consultation more than their experienced counterparts (Fye et.al., 2020). Therefore, further exploration of the construct with emphasis on how supervision (or lack thereof) impacts young professionals early in their counselling careers in international contexts is necessary.

4.2.2. Role Ambiguity, Workload, and Interference of Non-Counselling Duties

Role ambiguity was tested through questions asking whether additional duties interfere with the core counselling responsibilities and workload. Workload and interference of non-counselling duties with core counselling responsibilities were positively correlated with perceived level of burnout in the current sample: the more extra duties participants had on top of their core counselling work, which arguably amounted to higher workload, the higher levels of burnout they experienced. This is consistent with previous research confirming that role conflict and role ambiguity has a significant impact on burnout in school counsellors (Bardhoshi et al, 2014; Lee et al., 2007; Kendrick et.al., 1994; Moyer, 2011; Wilkerson, 2009). The researchers note that lack of role definition and set of job responsibilities results in every stakeholder (inclusive of school counsellors themselves) understanding the role differently (Burnham and Jackson, 2000), which in turn results in less time to work with the students and more time taken up by administrative paperwork (Bardhoshi et.al., 2014; Gysbers and Henderson, 2001) and an expectation to engage in tasks outside of their perceived responsibilities (Cervoni and DeLucia-Waack, 2011; Lieberman, 2004). The extra responsibilities may result in school counsellors feeling overworked, leading to job stress and burnout (Bardhoshi et al, 2014; Moyer, 2011; Wilkerson, 2009). Similar feelings were reported by participants through open questions:

“I often think the expectation arises from management not fully understanding my role.” (Participant 136, Lines 5-6)

“Administrators all have different ideas of what counselors' responsibilities should be.” (Participant 101, Line 5)

Similar to age, while role ambiguity was a significant factor in predicting burnout when tested against other demographic variables, the significance was offset upon introduction of additional job satisfaction elements, suggesting that satisfaction with one's job may offset the extra tasks school counsellors may find themselves engaged in. Upon closer examination, however, workload has remained a significant predictor of burnout throughout, thus making it unclear whether extra duties do play a role, or burnout related to heavier workload is linked to core counselling responsibilities alone. This therefore highlights a need for further investigation of the construct to determine what exactly signifies significant stressors in relation to role ambiguity and workload.

The fact that international school counsellors are expected to be proficient in various counselling approaches (Leung, 2003; Inman et.al., 2009) to meet diverse needs of students and student concerns (Gysbers, 2004; Wilkerson, 2009), possess multicultural awareness (Rivera et.al., 2008; Sakiz and Sarıçalı, 2018), and keep up to date with developments in the field (Gysbers and Henderson, 2012; Sakiz and Sarıçalı, 2018; Slaten and Baskin, 2014), may explain this finding; even if school counsellors are able to dedicate 100% of their time completing counselling-related tasks, the demands of the job may be amplified by immense diversity in student needs.

Nevertheless, the findings suggest that workload and role ambiguity are significant in predicting burnout in the current sample of international school counsellors. It is therefore imperative to develop a unified role definition in order to educate stakeholders involved in making decisions with regard to assignment of duties and responsibilities.

4.2.3 Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction was the strongest predictor of burnout in the current sample, with participants revealing feeling overall ambivalence towards their jobs. All of the

subscales of JSS (Spector, 1985) showed statistically significant negative correlations in relation to burnout, suggesting that as perceived level of satisfaction with one's job decreased, reported levels of burnout increased.

Addition of the job satisfaction variable uniquely accounted for 43% of variance in predicting level of burnout in the current sample. While all subscales of JSS showed a significant relationship with burnout, upon examining the statistical significance of the predictive value of each subscale, pay, fringe benefits, co-workers, nature of work, communication, and workload emerged as significant predictors of burnout in the current sample.

These findings are supported by previous research into the relationship between the two constructs (Maslach et al., 1996), linking low levels of job satisfaction with high levels of burnout in counselling and therapeutic populations in particular (Baggerly and Osborn, 2006; Bryant and Constantine, 2006; Fye et.al., 2020). Positive perception of the work environment, positive relationships with colleagues and supervisor, feeling involved in work, sense of autonomy, and clarity of job description and responsibilities have been linked with higher job satisfaction and lower levels of emotional exhaustion (Belicki and Woolcott, 1996; Brewer and Clippard, 2002; Kolodinsky et.al., 2009).

4.2.3.i. Salary

Pay has not been previously discussed as a factor in relation to burnout in school counsellors revealing a huge gap in existing research. Only a handful of studies included salary as a factor (Gambrell et.al., 2011; Gnilka et.al. 2015; Moro and Scherer), however, it was not discussed. Pay emerged as a statistically significant factor in predicting burnout in the current sample of international school counsellors, and was also highlighted in answers through open questions:

“Salary and benefits lead to my dissatisfaction at work, not other factors.”
(Participant 145, Lines 3-4)

“Our benefits [...] did not create balance for what was being asked of us and I often felt emotionally exhausted after work.” (Participant 74, Lines 4-5)

Commentary from Participant 74 perfectly illustrates one of the potential reasons for this, through the notion that unrealistic expectations (linked to role ambiguity and workload), may lead to feeling of not being fairly compensated for their work. It may be argued that expatriate professionals sacrifice the proximity to family and friends, and security and comfort of their home countries (Shortland, 2015) in exchange for financial incentives and savings potential (Fong, 2018; McEvoy and Buller, 2013). This finding suggests that there is a potentially significant link to the context international school counsellors operate in, highlighting the necessity for future research to include salary as a factor pertinent in discussion among international school counsellors.

4.2.3.ii. Workload and Nature of Work

Workload and nature of work, which described the job tasks themselves, emerged as significant predictors of burnout and have been discussed in more detail earlier in this section. Higher workload and lower levels of satisfaction with the job tasks themselves leads to higher levels of burnout. This is not unique to the international context, and current findings are supported by previous research (Baggerly and Osborn, 2006; Bardhoshi et al, 2014; Moyer, 2011; Wilkerson, 2009).

4.2.3.iii. Fringe Benefits

Fringe benefits, which include monetary and non-monetary benefits, emerged as a factor in predicting burnout in the current sample. School counsellors hold a unique position in a school: while not core teaching staff, school counsellors are involved in the delivery of counselling and career guidance curricula (Cinotti, 2014; Lambie and Williamson, 2004). While teachers do not directly report to school counsellors, they are considered members of the leadership team and may contribute to policymaking within the school (ASCA, 2005; Shillingford and Lambie, 2010; Stone and Clark, 2001). Because of this, school counsellors may be expected to adhere to an administrator's contractual obligation (inclusive of reduced holiday break to attend conferences and increased working hours), rather than a teacher's, although this differs from school to school (Mullen et.al., 2017; Ribak-Rosenthal, 1994; Scarborough and Culbreth, 2008). Moreover, due to its unique position, there is little opportunity for promotion and growth within the organisation (Fye et.al., 2020).

Taking all of these factors into account, fringe benefits may be the only “perk” school counsellors experience. Such benefits may include taking time off in lieu following conference attendance, and not adhering to clock-in clock-out culture, as many school and university guidance counsellors are expected to attend and organise after school events and host admissions officers. Fewer perceived fringe benefits and less satisfaction in available benefits undoubtedly leads to higher levels of burnout.

4.2.3.iv. Co-workers and Communication

Negative relationships along with perceived incompetence of colleagues, and low levels of satisfaction in communication within the school emerged as significant predictors in burnout in the current sample of international school counsellors.

Quantitative findings are complemented by qualitative commentary:

“[...] I feel that low levels of job satisfaction were related more to difficult relationships in the workplace.” (Participant 142, Lines 2-3)

“At this present International school it is a toxic workplace. People are in survival mode and throw each other under the bus. Backstabbing and awful leadership make everyday [sic] hard for me.” (Participant 17, Lines 4-6)

“Overall, the job itself is enjoyable. It is the lack of cohesion within our team that has been a source of energy drain.” (Participant 147, Lines 2-3)

The findings are supported by previous literature, where positive collegial relationships were posited to act as a safeguard against burnout in school counsellors (Bardhoshi et.al., 2014; Clemens et.al., 2009; Leinbaugh et.al., 2003). Moreover, researchers identified that organisational support was among the top influencing factors in burnout (Lambie, 2007), with higher-quality relationships with co-workers (Clemens et.al., 2009) and satisfaction with administrative and collegial support (Varlas, 2013; Mullen et al., 2017; Mullen et.al., 2021) resulting in higher levels of job satisfaction and lower levels of burnout.

Arguably, relationships with colleagues are paramount in expat communities, as individuals find themselves in unfamiliar settings, and may have limited access to people of a similar cultural and language background, meaning immediate relationships with colleagues may serve as the only available avenue of friendship.

Transparency and clarity of intra-organisational culture and communication is complex as is, however, there is arguably an additional challenge when schools operate internationally, where complexities of navigating the local culture and expectations are added to day-to-day responsibilities.

The findings are supported by previous research (Anderson, 2008; Clemens et.al., 2009) and suggest that in order to decrease levels of burnout in international school counsellors, it is imperative for schools to frequently communicate with their stakeholders with regard to their direction and policies.

Findings of the current study suggest that having a better understanding of job satisfaction may reduce levels of burnout in international school counsellors, with some factors acting as considerable safeguards against burnout (Bryant and Constantine, 2006).

4.2.4. Region

Interestingly, region did not emerge as a significant factor in predicting burnout in the current sample of international school and careers counsellors, suggesting that factors associated with burnout are not necessarily linked to region. Though some did emerge as significant in analysis of variance ([Table 18](#)), it may be difficult to generalise due to the small representative number of participants. Nevertheless, the findings in the current research may give an indication of trends specific to international school counsellors operating in a particular region. More research is therefore needed to examine these in greater depth.

4.3. RESEARCH QUESTION TWO: Factors influencing turnover intentions in international school and university guidance counsellors.

Previous research examined burnout and job satisfaction in relation to turnover intentions (Clemens et.al., 2009; Knudsen et.al., 2006; Mullen et.al., 2020), and turnover intention has been established as a precursor to actual turnover (Griffeth et.al., 2000; Mobley, 1977; Parasuraman, 1982). While annual turnover rates in international education have been examined, the focus has largely been on teaching staff (Mancuso

et.al., 2010; Odland and Ruzicka, 2009; Reeves and Wigford, 2008). With mixed findings reported by previous research (Desroches, 2013; Mancuso et.al., 2010; Oddland and Ruzicka, 2009), but arguably high annual turnover rates experienced by international schools (averaging 30%, Bunnell; 2014; Roberts et.al., 2010), the current study explored demographic, psychological, and environmental factors to determine whether they had significance in influencing and predicting turnover in the current sample of international school and university guidance counsellors.

Null hypothesis 2 was rejected for research question two, as a number of statistically significant correlations emerged as factors explaining turnover intentions in the current sample. Additional regression analysis demonstrated statistical significance in explaining the predictive value of several demographic, psychological, and environmental factors that were tested.

With the exception of region, no other demographic factor was correlated with turnover intentions in the current sample. Overall job satisfaction and overall counsellor burnout showed positive correlation with turnover intentions. All subscales of JSS (pay, promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, operating conditions, co-workers, nature of work, and communication) (JSS; Spector, 1985) were negatively correlated with turnover intentions, while three out of five domains of counsellor burnout inventory (exhaustion, negative work environment, and deterioration to personal life) (CBI; Lee et.al., 2007) showed positive correlation with turnover intention.

Upon closer examination of variance, once all demographic, psychological, and emotional factors were included in the model, four factors emerged as statistically significant predictors of turnover intention in the current sample. These were region, operating conditions, communication, and curriculum implementation.

Of note, while interference of extra duties showed significance when tested alongside demographic variables, and workload showed significance when job satisfaction was tested, both factors were mediated when the burnout variable was introduced to the model. Introducing the burnout variable uniquely explained 1% of predicting turnover intention in the current sample: it revealed that although school counsellors experience overwork, overwork itself is not what leads to turnover

intentions. Rather, it is how those feelings are managed that may lead to the intention of leaving one's job. Believing in one's competence in the job (CBI Incompetence) and caring for the client (CBI Devaluing Client) in particular may safeguard against feeling overworked, and, consequently, turnover intention. A similar theory was put forward by Mullen and Gutierrez (2016), and later supported by Mullen et. al. (2017), in relation to burnout and job satisfaction.

4.3.1. Curriculum Implementation

ASCA (2005) provides a framework of practice for school counsellors and is arguably most implemented by professionals working in international schools. Nevertheless, despite existing guidelines, school counsellors face a lack of role clarity or set job responsibilities, and a lack of understanding of what the role entails from students, teachers, and administrators, who may not be aware of the time needed in implementing comprehensive guidance curricula but are responsible for the assignment of duties (Baggerly and Osborn, 2006; Brown et.al., 2011; Fye et.al., 2020; Moyer, 2011; Paisley and McMahon, 2001). Although varied from school to school, this in turn may lead to increase in workload, lack of time to see students, lack of time to implement counselling curriculum, and potential burnout (Carey et.al., 2017; Cunningham and Sandhu, 2000; Gysbers, 2004; Inman et.al., 2009; Paisley and McMahon, 2001; Sakiz and Sarıçalı, 2018).

The results of the current study support previous research in reflecting that insufficient time to implement the counselling curriculum led to increase in turnover intentions in the current sample. This was complemented by qualitative responses, which also highlighted the varied context:

“[...] leads to lack of clarity and stability for our program.” (Participant 147, Lines 4-5)

“Not having specific time to see students interferes with my ability to provide a comprehensive counselling program.” (Participant 85, Lines 4-5)

School counsellors are already expected to be proficient in various counselling approaches to cater to diverse student needs (Inman et.al., 2009; Lee-Man and Luk-Fong, 2013; Leung, 2003). However, there may be an additional challenge for school

counsellors in international placements; not only are counsellors expected to keep up to date with the developments in the current practice and adhere to standards of accreditation bodies (Gysbers and Henderson, 2012; Slaten and Baskin, 2014), they are also expected to “possess considerable multicultural awareness” (Sakiz and Sariçalı, 2018; Rivera et.al., 2008) and display sensitivity when working with multiracial communities served by the school in which they operate (Green and Keys, 2001; Sakiz and Sariçalı, 2018). Moreover, researchers argue that cultural awareness should be reflected in the counselling curriculum (Sakiz and Sariçalı, 2018), as currently the models that are used for guidance are “transferred directly from the Western approaches” (Mocan-Aydin, 2000; Sakiz and Sariçalı; 2018). This has been highlighted and partially addressed by Rivera et.al. (2008). In their study on career guidance curriculum implementation in schools in Singapore, the researchers found that several modifications to the curriculum were necessary to cater to cultural differences in Singaporean communities (Rivera et.al., 2008; Torres-Rivera and Krupski, 2005), and that the adjustments took a significant amount of time.

Therefore, school counsellors in international schools not only require the specific time in which they can see the students to teach the curriculum, but also time to plan and potentially adjust to the needs of the multiracial demographic the school serves. This is not new, and has been previously expressed through the body of literature on implementation and efficacy of school guidance programmes (Paisley and McMahon, 2001; Gysbers and Henderson, 2012; Sakiz and Sariçalı, 2018), and the lack of a practical plan for curriculum implementation has been a topic of discussion for the last two decades (Gysbers and Henderson, 2012; Sakiz and Sariçalı, 2018). Moreover, studies highlighted that the success of counselling and guidance programmes in schools is hindered if there are frequent changes in personnel (Desroches, 2013; Gysbers and Henderson, 2012).

Thus, if international schools want to see success in these programmes, they must plan for retention of staff who are responsible for their delivery. Retention of school counselling staff in particular may be aided by giving the professionals sufficient time for planning and implementation of guidance curricula.

4.3.2. Communication and Operating Conditions

Operating conditions is related to policies and procedures, while communication refers to intra-organisational communication (Spector, 1985). Arguably, both are organisational factors addressed by senior leadership, on which others have little to no influence.

Early research examining organisational factors in relation to turnover, job satisfaction, and burnout introduced two notions when describing organisational structures: centralised and decentralised. Centralised structures were entirely hierarchical, where employees were not involved in decision-making (Hage and Aiken, 1967), whereas decentralised structures involved employees in decision-making (Osterman, 2000). They discovered that employees who felt involved in the organisational decision-making showed higher levels of job satisfaction (Finlay et.al., 1995; Knudsen et.al., 2006), while centralised structures led to greater stress and job dissatisfaction (Karasek, 1979; Knudsen et.al., 2006). Cropanzano et.al. (1997) further defined two organisational environments: political (competitive) and supportive (helpful). Employees in a political environment perceived it as hostile and were more likely to leave that organisation (Brewer and Clippard, 2002). Similar findings were reported in therapeutic communities (Knudsen et.al., 2006). Thus, centralised structures with competitive organisational environments are inducive of job stress, dissatisfaction, and burnout, which may in turn lead to the intention to leave the organisation.

Findings of the current study support previous research, with both factors (operating conditions and communication) emerged as statistically significant predictors of turnover intentions, and communication in particular showing a consistent relationship throughout all stages of the variance model.

Elements pertinent to operating conditions were revealed in participants' commentary:

“No discipline or policies and procedures. Child protection is not done well which all impacts on my daily work.” (Participant 17, Lines 6-8)

“Because of all of the bureaucracy and red tape at my school, I often feel dissuaded from taking on cool new projects.” (Participant 78, Lines 2-3)

Work culture and environment were also highlighted:

“I don’t feel like I can trust anyone at my job, as I’ve been in multiple meetings where other people are talked about negatively. I have already put [in] my notice [...]” (Participant 76, Lines 6-8)

“My turnover intentions are more so related to school climate and staff rather than roles of my job.” (Participant 85, Lines 4-5)

The findings of the current study imply that organisational factors are significant in influencing the decision for international school counsellors to leave their placement. Reportedly high turnover rates in counselling professions (Gallon et.al., 2003; Knudsen et.al., 2006), with potential shortage of school counsellors (Clemens et.al., 2009), and looming concern over the state of affairs in the international school market (Desroches, 2013; Gilbert, 2011; Mancuso et.al., 2010; Reeves and Wigford, 2008), highlight an imperative for international schools to address the existing conditions. Understanding and transparency of schools concerning the structure and environment, frequent communication with regard to the school’s mission, and clear policies and procedures may significantly reduce turnover intentions in international school counsellors.

4.3.3. Region

Region emerged as a significant predictor of turnover intention in the current sample of international school counsellors in all models of statistical testing. The significance of region was discovered through correlational analysis and analysis of variance, with region remaining statistically strong and consistent throughout. Additional analysis showed that all geographical regions presented specific areas of concern ([Table 17](#)).

Though difficult to generalise due to the small representative sample, the results of the current study present an overview of the trends and areas of concern connected to particular geographical regions, which warrant further investigation.

The significance of region may be interlinked with communication and operating conditions, since both factors remained consistent in all testing models in the current study. This calls for more transparency in communication of international schools in order to attract and retain the right personnel.

4.3.4. Additional Impressions

While pay and promotion is significantly negatively correlated with turnover intentions, neither factor is significant in predicting turnover intentions according to the model of variance. This may be due to particular demographics of the current sample: as the majority of the respondents were in their 40s, with over ten years of experience, an assumption can be made that they are mid-career professionals who are not on entry levels wages. As such, their decision to leave the current placement would be less likely to be affected by the desire for advancement in salary. Moreover, it has been posited that school counselling professionals may have limited opportunities for advancement and promotion due to schools often employing a single counsellor to accommodate the whole school (Davis et.al., 2006; Gambrell et.al., 2011).

Open questions provided an opportunity for the participants to state their reasons for leaving their current position. Various reasons were given: negative work environment, pursuit of new career, personal reasons, and lack of promotion opportunities. This is consistent with previous research citing the following reasons: personal (Brummitt and Keeling, 2013; Hayden, 2011; Mancuso et.al., 2010; Odland and Ruzicka, 2009), overwork, termination of career, work culture, operating conditions (Desroches, 2013; Fontaine et al., 2012) ineffective leadership (Mancuso et.al., 2010; Odland and Ruzicka, 2009).

In addition to the above, two unique factors emerged – returning to home country, and ready to go to a different country:

“I am planning to leave my job this year [...] I'm just ready to move back to the US and be closer to my family.” (Participant 32, Lines 7-8)

“Leaving this job because ready to move to a new country.”
(Participant 50, Line 2)

This may be a particularly unique factor in international expat communities. Living and working abroad has become easier over the past two decades (Creemers et. al, 2002; Lauder, 2007; Song et.al, 2016; Yen, 2008). Acceptable high turnover rates (Bunnell, 2014; Roberts et.al., 2010), where it is expected that expatriate educators

spend 2.5 years at one school on average (Benson, 2011; Mancuso et.al., 2010), make it easier to hop from school to school and explore different cultures, countries and continents. The obverse is that the desire to be closer to family and friends may eventually take dominance over the sense of adventure. Moreover, due to the study being conducted in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic, this context may have resulted in an increased desire to remain close to family (Feinberg et.al., 2021; Zhang, 2020).

Qualitative data provided more contextual background to the question at hand. Nevertheless, the variety of responses also highlighted how contextualised and personal the turnover decisions are. More research is therefore needed to examine the construct in greater depth.

4.4. RESEARCH QUESTION THREE: Significance of region in burnout and turnover intentions in international school counsellors.

Region did not emerge as a significant factor in predicting burnout, through correlations or through analysis of variance, therefore the null hypothesis 3(a) was accepted, and it was concluded that region was not a significant factor in predicting burnout in the current sample of international school counsellors. Upon investigation of each variable broken down by region, some strong trends did emerge ([Table 18](#)), highlighting areas of concern in particular regions. However, current data made it difficult to be generalised due to the small number of participants. Further investigation with a larger sample is therefore necessary to draw conclusions.

Region emerged a significant predictor of turnover intentions, and alternative hypothesis 3(b) was accepted in confirming that region does play a significant role in predicting turnover intentions in the current sample of international school counsellors. Additional regression model was applied, and influence of variance was additionally broken down by region, revealing all geographical regions presented areas of concern ([Table 17](#)). In-depth investigation is necessary to discover a more nuanced relationship between region and turnover intentions. Moreover, larger samples of participants are needed to investigate particular trends within geographical regions. Nevertheless,

significant regional findings may be difficult to generalise due to the small sample size. The uncovered trend may pave the way for areas to focus on in future research.

Findings of the current study indicate that while region is not a significant factor in predicting burnout, it plays a significant role in predicting turnover intentions in international school counsellors. No research to date has examined the significance of region in this population, therefore highlighting a major gap in previous research and warranting further investigation.

CHAPTER 5. IMPLICATIONS AND DIRECTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Findings of the current study have high relevance to the field of international school educators, in particular those in school counselling and university guidance. As school counsellors are directly responsible for inception, planning, and delivery of social-emotional programmes and career guidance that directly impacts students and all relevant stakeholders, it is imperative to give attention to how international school counsellors experience wellbeing, burnout and job satisfaction (Davis et al., 2006; Leinbaugh et al., 2003). The aim of the study was to develop a clearer understanding of burnout and turnover intentions in these communities, and to pave the way for future investigation into developing strategies to support the populations in question.

As burnout is seemingly an unavoidable phenomenon in counselling professions (Kesler, 1990; Lambie, 2007), more training in self-care strategies (Mullen et.al., 2018) and ways to assess burnout to ensure self-awareness (Bradley et.al., 2013; Mullen et.al., 2018) may be necessary early on in the profession and throughout the career to help prevent job dissatisfaction.

The findings of the current study revealed that early career school counsellors experienced higher levels of burnout, therefore a review of current systems is necessary to incorporate the needs of younger and less experienced school and university guidance counsellors entering the profession. Future research may also consider the role consultation has in acting as a protective measure against burnout, particularly in early career professionals.

Role ambiguity, workload, and interference of non-counselling duties call for international schools, international bodies, and governing organisations to come together to review current role definitions, and to create a unified one. Moreover, it is necessary to educate stakeholders with regard to the role and responsibilities of school and university guidance counsellors to prevent excessive assignment of non-counselling duties, leading to increased job stress as a result.

The job satisfaction domains salary and fringe benefits have not been investigated in depth in the school counselling populations and have not been investigated in international school counsellors. Both constructs emerged as significant

predictors of burnout in the current sample, unveiling an aspect relevant to international school counsellors, warranting further investigation into reasons of satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the benefits package and its relation to burnout.

Finally, negative relationships with colleagues and low levels of satisfaction with communication within the school were significant in predicting burnout in the current sample of international school counsellors. This highlights the importance of work culture and environment (Bardhoshi et.al., 2014; Clemens et.al., 2009; Leinbaugh et.al., 2003; Mullen et al., 2018; Mullen et.al., 2021), and calls for frequent and transparent communication of the school with their stakeholders with regard to their direction and policies (Bryant and Constantine, 2006; Clemens et.al., 2009).

Geographical region of the school and organisational factors (communication and operating conditions) showed significance in predicting turnover intention. The findings highlight the need for international schools to reflect on and address current operating conditions; transparency concerning school structure and environment, frequent communication with stakeholders, and clear policies and procedures may aid in reducing turnover intentions and retaining school counsellors. Further study with larger regional samples is necessary to explain effects of burnout and job satisfaction as predictors of turnover intentions within each geographical region. Moreover, future researchers may investigate parallels in burnout and turnover intentions in international and local schools to provide additional regional background and context.

Findings of this study will be disseminated at IACAC'21 and ISCA'21 virtual conferences. The conferences offer a space for members to learn about research and the current state of affairs in international school and university guidance, as well as providing a forum to discuss how members can support wellness, in the hope of moving towards a more sustainable and fulfilling work environment.

CHAPTER 6: LIMITATIONS AND CONCLUSION

6.1. LIMITATIONS

Due to the nature of the study, there were a number of limitations that affected recruitment and participation. The study limited its outreach to current members of the largest international counselling organisations – ISCA and IACAC. School counsellors outside of those networks may have had different experiences.

The current study implemented survey design with self-report data, which is susceptible to social desirability bias (Heppner, et.al., 1999; Lucas and Baird, 2006; Rosenman et.al., 2011). Moreover, while online surveys provide convenient access, a limitation of multiple-choice questions may have resulted in quick responses without properly reading the questions asked (Börger, 2016). Therefore, caution should be exercised when interpreting results (Lefever et al., 2007; Wright, 2005).

The majority of participants were female ($n = 111$, 70.25%), in their 40s ($n = 66$, 41.8%), with over 10 years of experience in the field ($n = 69$, 43.67%). It is therefore possible that results obtained have diminished significance for some factors. Future research should consider diversifying the sample, attempting to engage less experienced younger professionals as well as the male demographic to obtain more representative findings. Moreover, attempts should be made to invite participants from lesser represented geographical regions ([Table 1](#), [Figure 3](#)).

The invitation to participate in the survey was sent out during the months of December and January, which are usually marked by high levels of stress among school staff (Borg, 1990; Mäkinen and Kinnunen, 1986) with December being a taxing month marking the end of the school term, and January signifying the beginning of the term with a potential increased workload (Borg, 1990; Mäkinen and Kinnunen, 1986). The time from mid-December to mid-January, also usually reflects when schools often have their winter holidays, so potential participants may have dismissed the email, or not have checked it during their break.

Moreover, the study was conducted during the global COVID-19 pandemic, with most countries implementing a lock-down at the time the survey invitation was sent out (Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker (OxCGRT); Hale et.al.,

2021). Though attempts were made to “COVID-proof” the study, it can be argued that the daily stressors of living in the time of the pandemic had an impact on the willingness of individuals to take part. Additionally, because of COVID-19, the significant negative findings may have been exacerbated by the pressures on international schools put in place by local governments (OxCGRT; Hale et.al., 2021). Nevertheless, it can be argued that many of these issues were already present pre-COVID-19 pandemic and were simply made more apparent due to the heightened pressures this period presented.

Quantitative methodology was implemented to address the research questions in the study, as it was deemed most suitable in providing initial insight and overview of experiences (Mujis, 2004; Cohen et al., 2007). The research questions were created precisely for this purpose and were not suited for qualitative inquiry. An attempt was made to address more personal experience of burnout through two open-ended questions, and a total of 129 open-ended responses were collected. However, there was no opportunity provided to participants for follow-up, and due to the nature of research questions qualitative data was not analysed in-depth in the current study. Nevertheless, open-ended questions helped to contextualise responses recorded through the qualitative measure (Friborg and Rosenvinge, 2013; Hanson et.al., 2005) and are discussed to support quantitative findings. Future research should consider implementing multi-method design or qualitative methodology with semi-structured interviews to gain insight into personal experiences and further examine factors contributing to burnout and turnover intentions in international school counsellors.

Finally, participants were able to select different roles they were involved in at their workplace to address the issues of role ambiguity. Further deconstruction of specific roles and specialisations may be necessary, as school counsellors operating in different grade levels, or concerned with career counselling alone, may have different experiences of burnout, job satisfaction, and turnover intentions (Gnilka et.al., 2015).

6.2. CONCLUSION

This study examined factors influencing burnout and turnover intentions in international school and university guidance counsellors. This is the first study to date to examine burnout and turnover intentions in this community.

Findings indicated that school and university guidance counsellors experienced overall ambivalence toward their jobs and moderate to high levels of burnout. Age and experience emerged as significant factors in predicting burnout, with early career school and university guidance counsellors being particularly vulnerable, while job satisfaction was the strongest predictor of burnout across all age groups. In particular, dissatisfaction with salary, fringe benefits, job tasks themselves, intra-school communication, relationships with co-workers, and higher workload led to higher levels of burnout.

Turnover intentions were exacerbated by dissatisfaction with operating conditions, lack of time to implement counselling curriculum, ineffective intra-organisational communication, and the geographical region in which school counsellors were based. Burnout, however, was not a significant factor in predicting turnover intentions.

The results of the study shed light on the challenges faced by school counsellors operating internationally and suggest that current practice does not meet the needs of early career professionals, therefore additional training, supervision, or mentorship programmes may help to decrease burnout in these professionals.

Considering the significance of job satisfaction, it is paramount that international schools review current policies with regard to remuneration, operating conditions, work culture, and intra-organisational communication to reduce burnout and turnover intentions in these communities.

Finally, regional significance suggests further transparency, frequent communication, and regional/cultural education for applicants is necessary to ensure they are aware of cultural and regional challenges they may face, which could help to reduce job stress and turnover intentions in school and university counselling staff.

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